

UNITED STATES OF AMERICA
DEPARTMENT OF HEALTH AND HUMAN SERVICES
FOOD AND DRUG ADMINISTRATION
CENTER FOR BIOLOGICS EVALUATION AND RESEARCH

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VACCINES AND RELATED BIOLOGICAL PRODUCTS
ADVISORY COMMITTEE

+ + + + +

OPEN SESSION

+ + + + +

WEDNESDAY,

NOVEMBER 28, 2001

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The Advisory Committee was called to order at 1:54 p.m., in the Versailles Ballrooms I and II, of the Holiday Inn-Bethesda, 8120 Wisconsin Avenue, Bethesda, Maryland by Dr. Robert S. Daum, Chairman, presiding.

PRESENT:

DR. ROBERT S. DAUM, Chairman

DR. WALTER L. FAGGETT, Member

DR. BARBARA LOE FISHER, Member

DR. JUDITH D. GOLDBERG, Member

DR. DIANE E. GRIFFIN, Member

DR. SAMUEL L. KATZ, Member

DR. KWANG SIK KIM, Member

DR. STEVE KOHL, Member

DR. PETER PALESE, Member

DR. DIXIE E. SNIDER, JR., Member

DR. DAVID S. STEPHENS, Member

DR. JUAN FELIX, Invited Participant

DR. THOMAS FLEMING, Invited Participant

DR. RALPH FREEDMAN, Invited Participant

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DR. MICHAEL GREENE, Invited Participant
PRESENT: (CONT.)

DR. PAMELA MCINNES, Invited Participant
DR. MARTIN MYERS, Invited Participant
DR. DENNIS O'CONNOR, Invited Participant
DR. SONIA PAGLIUSI, Invited Participant
DR. WILLIAM REEVES, Invited Participant
DR. ELLEN SHEETS, Invited Participant
DR. ELIZABETH UNGER, Invited Participant
DR. EDWARD WILKINSON, Invited Participant

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I-N-D-E-X

Vaccine for the Prevention of Human Papilloma Virus

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P-R-O-C-E-E-D-I-N-G-S

(1:54 p.m.)

CHAIRMAN DAUM: If everybody would take their places and settle down, please. Good afternoon, and welcome to the open session. We will begin by calling on Nancy Cherry for a conflict of interest statement.

MS. CHERRY: While I am reading this, it would be a good time for those of you who are at the table and standing to turn off your cell phones, or to put your pagers on silent.

The following announcement addresses conflict of interest issues associated with the Vaccines and Related Biological Products Advisory Committee meeting on November 28th, 2001.

Should there be any voting during this session on HPV, the Director of the Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research has appointed Drs. Thomas Fleming, Pamela McInnes, Martin Myers, Dennis O'Connor, William Reeves, Ellen Sheets, Elizabeth Unger, and Edward Wilkinson, as temporary voting members for this session.

To determine whether any conflict of interests exist, the agency reviewed the submitted agenda and all financial interests reported by the meeting participants. As a result of this review, the following disclosures are being made.

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1 Drs. Palese, Fleming, and Freedman each have
2 been granted a waiver in accordance with current statutes
3 which permit them to participate fully in the discussions.

4 Drs. Daum, Griffin, Stephens, Fleming,
5 Freedman, O'Connor, Sheets, and Unger have associations
6 with firms that could be or appear to be affected by the
7 committee discussions.

8 However, in accordance with current
9 statutes, it has been determined that none of these
10 associations is sufficient to warrant the need for a
11 waiver or an exclusion.

12 In the event that the discussions involve
13 specific products or firms not on the agenda, and for
14 which FDA's participants have a financial interest, the
15 participants are reminded of the need to exclude
16 themselves from the discussion, and the recusals will
17 be noted for the public record.

18 With respect to all other meetings, we would
19 ask in the interest of fairness that you say your name
20 and affiliation, and any current or previous financial
21 involvement with any firm whose products you wish to
22 comment on.

23 Copies of all waivers addressed in this
24 announcement are available by written request under the
25 Freedom of Information Act.

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1 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much, Nancy.
2 It is an always scintillating Conflict of Interest
3 Report. Well, I think we will now just very briefly ask
4 the Committee to introduce themselves to people who have
5 not been here all day. And, David, if you wouldn't mind,
6 we will start with you.

7 DR. STEPHENS: Dave Stephens, Emory
8 University, in Atlanta.

9 DR. KOHL: Steve Kohl, Oregon Health Science
10 University.

11 DR. GRIFFIN: Diane Griffin, Johns Hopkins.

12 DR. SNIDER: Dixie Snider, Centers for
13 Disease Control and Prevention.

14 DR. KIM: Kwang Sik Kim, Johns Hopkins.

15 DR. KATZ: Samuel Katz, Duke University.

16 DR. PALESE: Peter Palese, Mount Sinai
17 School of Medicine, New York.

18 DR. MYERS: Mark Myers, National Vaccine
19 Program Office.

20 DR. MCINNES: Pamela McInnes, National
21 Institute of Virology and Infectious Diseases.

22 DR. O'CONNOR: Dennis O'Connor, Clinical
23 Associates, Louisville, Kentucky.

24 DR. REEVES: Bill Reeves, Centers for
25 Disease Control and Prevention.

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1 DR. GOLDBERG: Judy Goldberg, New York
2 University.

3 DR. FLEMING: Tom Fleming, University of
4 Washington.

5 DR. SHEETS: Ellen Sheets, Women's Hospital,
6 Boston.

7 DR. UNGER: Elizabeth Unger, Centers for
8 Disease Control and Prevention.

9 DR. WILKINSON: Edward Wilkinson,
10 University of Florida, College of Medicine.

11 DR. FELIX: Juan Felix, Tech School of
12 Medicine, University of Southern California.

13 DR. FREEDMAN: Ralph Freedman, Indiana
14 Cancer Center.

15 DR. GREENE: Mike Greene, Massachusetts
16 General Hospital, Boston.

17 DR. PAGLIUSI: Sonia Pagliusi, from Vaccines
18 and Biologicals, of the World Health Organization.

19 CHAIRMAN DAUM: And I am Robert Daum, from
20 the University of Chicago. And the FDA folks at the
21 table.

22 DR. GEBER: Antonia Geber, FDA.

23 DR. PRATT: Douglas Pratt, FDA.

24 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Karen Goldenthal, FDA.

25 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much. I

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1 think we will now begin with the business of the afternoon,
2 which is an open session to look at efficacy trial
3 endpoints for vaccines for the prevention of HPV.

4 And we will begin by calling on Dr. Goldenthal
5 from FDA to give us an introduction to the session, and
6 presentation of questions. Dr. Goldenthal.

7 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Thank you. Before we get
8 started on this afternoon's open session, I would like
9 to present the two questions to our advisory committee
10 and consultants.

11 The first is please discuss and identify the
12 most appropriate endpoints for traditional approval of
13 HPV vaccine intended to prevent cervical cancer. In
14 particular, please discuss the use of the following
15 endpoints and clinical trials intended to demonstrate
16 the efficacy of HPV vaccines for oncogenic types, and
17 the indications, for example, for prevention of HPV
18 infection that these endpoints would support.

19 Incident HPV infection by oncogenic HPV
20 types; that is, at least one positive HPV DNA test result.

21
22 Persistent HPV infection by oncogenic HPV
23 types. Regarding this endpoint, please also discuss the
24 appropriate number of positive virologic results in the
25 interval between positive virologic results.

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1 Next is LSIL cytology associated with
2 oncogenic HPV types. The next is CIN-1 associated with
3 oncogenic HPV types; CIN-2/3 associated with oncogenic
4 HPV types; and cervical cancers.

5 The second question is please discuss the
6 use of the accelerated approval regulations for licensure
7 of HPV vaccines for prevention of cervical cancers;
8 specifically, please discuss and identify possible
9 surrogate endpoints to support accelerated approvals.

10 In particular, consider the following
11 endpoints. Incident HPV infection by oncogenic HPV
12 types; persistent HPV infection by oncogenic HPV types;
13 LSIL cytology associated with oncogenic HPV types; and
14 CIN-1 associated with oncogenic HPV types.

15 In the context of accelerated approval,
16 please discuss and identify possible end points for the
17 confirmatory trials. Thank you. I think we can now
18 proceed to the first afternoon speaker.

19 CHAIRMAN DAUM: That was very succinct, Dr.
20 Goldenthal, and thank you. Dr. Unger, if we could get
21 started with your presentation on Natural History and
22 Virology.

23 DR. UNGER: Thank you very much. I feel like
24 we have covered this topic to some extent in almost every
25 presentation, and so I am going to emphasize those things

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1 that I think are most important, and this will be a lot
2 of repetition.

3 Papilloma viruses are not only human
4 papilloma viruses. They are widely distributed in higher
5 vertebrates, and there is a very tight specie specificity.

6 They are all very similar and they are
7 non-enveloped, double-standard DNA viruses, and they have
8 a small genom that is circular. It is a DNA genom, and
9 the viruses look very similar under electron microscopy.

10 They are 55 nanometer spherical capsid particles.

11 They all have tropism for squamous
12 epithelium. That is, they all tend to be found in
13 squamous epithelium, and they all are associated in their
14 specific hosts with the formation of warts and papillomas,
15 which are just growths of that squamous epithelium.

16 The genom organization is similar across all
17 of the species. Only one of the strands is transcribed,
18 and the open reading frames have been named in relation
19 to the bovine papilloma virus genoms, which was one of
20 the first species studied in-depth.

21 The early genes are named E-1 through E-7,
22 but there is no E-3 in HPV, and I have pondered that for
23 a long while, and I thought that I would get that out
24 of the way, just so that you are not looking for it.

25 The late genes are called L-1 and L-2, and

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1 these genes are those that code for the major and minor
2 capsid proteins. This is a schematic, and you will see
3 pictures like this repeatedly of the HPV genom in its
4 episomal form.

5 It could be basically any of the genoms that
6 I am showing, and this happens to be the one for HPV 16,
7 and it shows the circular arrangements and the little
8 P-97 is the most widely studied promoter region, and we
9 will come back to that.

10 This simple Genom means that the virus does
11 not have near enough genetic information to copy itself.

12 It is very dependent on the host cell for the machinery
13 for replication, transcription, and translation.

14 And it is because of that that the viral
15 functions are very tightly linked to cellular
16 differentiation, and the promoter region that I told you
17 is the one that is the one that is most often studied,
18 but there is very good evidence that there are other
19 promoter regions that can act and that they occur, and
20 they get turned on as a function of the differentiation
21 state of the cell.

22 All of the transcripts are also very poorly
23 understood. They are all poly-cistronic
24 bio-transcripts. That means that they are very long and
25 complicated, and they have multiple splice patterns, and

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1 the promoter usage as I mentioned before is very linked
2 to differentiation.

3 Now to talk about each of the little regions
4 in-turn. The HPV URRs is the upstream regulatory region.

5 It also is called -- sometimes you will see in the
6 literature the long controlled region, or the non-coding
7 region.

8 And this is really a very important because
9 it contains multiple transcriptional and replication
10 regulatory elements. And this is one area where the viral
11 genom interacts very tightly with the cell protein
12 machinery.

13 Late genes, as I mentioned before, the late
14 genes have the greatest genetic conservation among all
15 of the types, and the L-1 is the major capsid protein.

16 The capsid is formed of 72 pentamers of L-1, and when
17 L-1 is expressed in systems, the protein itself will form
18 spontaneously into viral like particles.

19 One thing that is very important about HPV
20 proteins are that it is the native conformational state
21 that is most important and relevant for immune response.

22 And so the fact that this virus will allow
23 the L-1 proteins to be formed into viral like particles
24 has been used in studies of the immune response. L-2
25 is a minor capsid protein, and in functional studies it

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1 appears to be required for actually incorporating the
2 viral DNA into the viral particle.

3 The early genes. I am just going to hit the
4 high points on them, and there are many more functions
5 that could be associated with them. But just briefly,
6 the E-1 is essential for viral replication, and it is
7 known to maintain that episome.

8 That is the small circular genom. The E-2
9 protein is important in transcriptional regulation, and
10 it is a co-factor for viral replication. E-2 has been
11 shown to have both promoter and inhibitory effects on
12 transcription, depending on the state.

13 E-4 apparently disrupts cytokekeratin, and it
14 is important in the shedding of the virus. E-5 interacts
15 with growth factor receptors; and E-6 and
16 E-7 have been mentioned several times this morning. And
17 they are the proteins that are characterized as
18 transforming proteins, important in P-53 degradation and
19 RB binding, respectively.

20 Now, of course, in the viral lifecycle,
21 transformation is really not a part of the intent from
22 a biologic point of view of the virus. So the function
23 of E-6 and E-7 in the lifecycle of the virus appears to
24 be one where the proteins prolong the dividing phase of
25 the cell.

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1 Viral replication and assembly occurs in the
2 nucleus of the infected cell. Infection, as far as we
3 can tell, is initiated in the basal epithelium cells.
4 That is the renewable compartment in the epithelium.

5 Steady state viral replication in some early
6 gene transcription occurs, and this is the site of the
7 presumed latent infection. And in animal model studies,
8 it has been recognized that the virus can persist in this
9 basal epithelium at very low copy number, with no
10 phenotypic change; that is, no apparent change in the
11 overlying epithelium.

12 There is some trigger, and again not very
13 well known, which leads to high copy viral replication
14 in late gene transcription and virion production, and
15 this occurs only in the differentiating cells.

16 Now, viral integration is not a normal part
17 of the viral lifecycle, but it is observed, and when it
18 occurs, it occurs randomly in the host chromosome. That
19 is, there is no one specific site in the cellular
20 chromosomes where it occurs.

21 But in the virus, it occurs at a
22 characteristic break point, and that is between E-1 and
23 E-2. The disruption in this region means that the E-6,
24 E-7 region, if you think back to that circular genom that
25 I showed you, is still intact, and that the region may

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1 not be normally regulated, and it is thought that this
2 abnormal expression of E-6, E-7 contributes to oncogenic
3 progression.

4 Now, viral integration is associated with
5 oncogenesis, but it is not absolutely required to the
6 best of our knowledge. The immune response to these
7 viruses is also very complicated.

8 The infection as I have mentioned is a
9 non-lytic infection. That means that the cells are not
10 degraded in the host. The virus is released with the
11 desquamating epithelium.

12 That means that the host has minimal exposure
13 to the virions, but it is well characterized from
14 observational studies that the immune system really does
15 influence the outcome of HPV infection, and just as one
16 simple example, immuno-compromised individuals have more
17 problems with warts and persistence of warts, and with
18 progression of cervical neoplasia.

19 There are both humoral and serologic
20 responses that are identified. Interestingly, not all
21 infected hosts -- that is, hosts in whom we have identified
22 HPV DNA -- will have a detectable serologic response with
23 current assays.

24 Now, in the human papilloma viruses, we have
25 alluded to this many times before, there are a whole lot

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1 of them, and there is more than a hundred different types
2 that have at least been partially characterized, and now
3 there are more than 80 that are fully sequenced.

4 All of the typing is based strictly upon the
5 nucleate assay sequence, and if there is less than 10
6 percent difference, it is considered part of the same
7 type.

8 If it is less than two percent, and if the
9 difference is on the order of two percent, it is considered
10 a variant, and as -- and you can imagine that there has
11 been a lot of investigation of sequencing of these
12 viruses.

13 There is increasing consensus that the
14 variance, that these small DNA changes could be important.

15 The types are assigned strictly on a sequential number,
16 which is based on the order of discovery, and this does
17 lead to some confusion.

18 There is absolutely no relationship in the
19 numbering to any kind of phylogeny, and that is just kind
20 of the way the world evolved. HPV types can be broken
21 down into two major phylogenetic branches based on their
22 different affinities for the site of infection.

23 HPV, the cutaneous types, affect the squamous
24 epithelium. They are the ones that are responsible for
25 the common hand and foot warts, and these cutaneous types

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1 probably are more numerous even than these mucosal types,
2 but they have been less studied.

3 And the mucosal types affect predominantly
4 a non-keratinized squamous epithelium, and there are more
5 than 30 of these types that are found in the anal/genital
6 tracts. And these are further kind of broken down into
7 what have been called low risk and high risk types.

8 Low risk types are those types that have been
9 rarely or never found in cancers, and high risk types
10 are those that have been frequently found in cancers.

11 Now, it is important to realize though that
12 the high risk types are the most prevalent in the
13 population, regardless of the disease status. And best
14 characterized for HPV 16 and that is because HPV 16 is
15 the most tightly linked with cervical cancer, accounting
16 for -- depending on the population -- approximately 60
17 percent of the cases.

18 The E-6/E-7 polymorphisms could modify
19 oncogenicity, but the variance have been cross-reactive
20 in most ELISA assays. Now, there are some unique features
21 about HPV that makes studying this virus difficult.

22 And first of all, if it has not been clear
23 before, there is no simple in vitro culture method. There
24 is no such thing as culturing for the virus. Antibody
25 methods lack sensitivity, at least in their current

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1 format.

2 So, therefore, diagnosing infection requires
3 the detection of HPV genetic information, and that means
4 that it requires a cellular sample from the site of
5 infection, and only current infections can be identified.

6 Now, infection, I would like to put in quotes,
7 because we are really not dealing with infection. We
8 are dealing with the detection of DNA, and we are assuming
9 that means infection.

10 Because we are limited by actually only
11 monitoring DNA, our view of the disease is totally framed
12 by the sample that is collected and by the assay that
13 is being done to analyze it.

14 And this complicates the study of latent,
15 occult persistent reoccurring infection, and it
16 complicates comparison of different kinds of studies,
17 and I am going to talk a little bit about the sample.

18 Tissue samples provide a direct correlation
19 between observed pathology and the virus. These samples
20 also include the basal epithelium, which is a place where
21 occult infection might be.

22 The problem is that only a limited area is
23 sampled, and one biopsy is a very small area, and this
24 is not a suitable method for any kind of screening or
25 large scale study.

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1 And therefore most studies that you are going
2 to read about utilize exfoliated cytology samples of one
3 form or another. This is a non-invasive approach for
4 screening the population, but you have to realize that
5 the sample is not specifically directed at a lesion.

6 It is collected to sample the area to be most
7 representative. The quality of the sample is very
8 dependent on the collection device that is used, and on
9 the anatomic site that is sampled.

10 And a whole variety of devices are available,
11 and the amount of yield of cells is varies with each of
12 those devices. You must keep in mind that the basal
13 epithelium is not usually sampled in this kind of
14 approach.

15 Now, in women, the cervix is the sample that
16 is most commonly used, and that is the site where the
17 pathology is. And the appropriate sample in males is
18 not at all clear.

19 Briefly, the estimates of HPV associated
20 disease in the United States is that it is an extremely
21 prevalent problem. This data really comes from Laura
22 Koutsky, and it is kind of a very broad extrapolation.

23
24 The bottom line is that probably 75 percent
25 of the population has been exposed to HPV at some point

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1 in their life. Genital HPV is acquired around the time
2 of sexual debut, and it is primarily a sexually
3 transmitted infection.

4 And infection is usually transient, and it
5 is usually not associated with symptoms. Persistent
6 infection and the definition of that we can talk about,
7 is the one that is most likely to be associated with the
8 potential for neoplasia.

9 Now, there has been a consistent
10 epidemiologic association of HPV with cervical cancer,
11 and cervical cancer pre-cursor lesions. There are
12 plausible biologic mechanisms for HPV oncogenesis, and
13 it should be kept in mind that this oncogenesis is a rare
14 event, with a long interval between infection and cancer.

15
16 So it is believed that infection alone is
17 insufficient to cause cancer, and additional factors are
18 required for neoplasia. There are certainly lots of
19 questions about HPV infection, and one of the most common
20 is HPV eliminated from the host.

21 HPV clearing again is monitored by DNA
22 detection and cytology samples, and negative results
23 indicate that shedding is below the limit of detection,
24 but the basal compartment may not be adequately sampled.

25 HPV can be detected in histologically normal

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1 margins surrounding growth lesions, and this is from older
2 studies where people have done biopsies and sampled the
3 basal epithelium.

4 The duration of infection is one that again
5 we have heard discussed. I have given two studies which
6 made an attempt to study incident infections, and then
7 followed how long to clearing, and the median for HPV
8 16 in the Woodman study was 10.3 months, and for HPV 18
9 it was 7 months.

10 And in the Franco study, where they lumped
11 the oncogenic types all together, it was 8.1 months.
12 So how does this kind of data inform us as to what should
13 we count as a persistent infection?

14 Currently, there is really no consistent on
15 definition. What is clear is that in order to talk about
16 a persistent infection, it requires detection of the same
17 HPV type on more than one occasion.

18 And that requires a time specific assay then,
19 and the time interval varies between 3 to 6 months, and
20 in longer intervals people talk about concerns about the
21 potential for reinfection, rather than a persistent
22 infection.

23 And consistent detection on each occasion
24 is one approach, versus intermittent detection, which
25 could then be a reflection of sampling and assay.

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1 Similarly, latent infection is a big question.

2 The formal definition of a latent infection
3 is the presence of HPV DNA and the absence of virion
4 production. But practically what it really means is a
5 section of HPV DNA in the absence of an identifiable
6 lesion.

7 And this is the situation of HPV DNA positive
8 normal cytology. But it is also equated with occult
9 infection. Now, the fact that there are multiple assays
10 really complicate or multiple types really complicate
11 HPV assays.

12 The sensitivity in the site type specificity
13 of the assays all vary, and inter-assay comparisons are
14 very difficult. The beginning of this field relied on
15 Southern blot and dot plot and in situ, and that plot
16 is like hybridizations.

17 And currently Hybrid Capture is another
18 example of a direct hybridization. Amplification
19 assays, such as PCR, can be either type specific or
20 directed at a broad spectrum of the virus.

21 And just briefly about the hybrid capture
22 assay. I feel like I can't ignore it. It is the current
23 FDA approved test. In 1999, it shifted into a micro-titer
24 format that uses liquid hybridization and it has a
25 chemiluminescent detection.

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1 The RNA probes react with the DNA targets,
2 and it groups the probes into high risk and low risk,
3 and does not have a type specific format at this point.

4 The signal is semi-quantitative, but there is no control
5 for the input amount of the DNA.

6 The probe mixes are as shown here, and this
7 assay here really shows very good inter-laboratory
8 comparison. It was really made to be a very vigorous
9 clinical assay, but again the results are not type
10 specific.

11 The hybrid-capture assay has been designed
12 primarily to work with exfoliated cervical samples and
13 the recommended collection includes the brush and the
14 sample transport media, and the sample includes both
15 endo-and-ectocervical cells.

16 And if you go through the calculations of
17 how much the sample is put into the assay, approximately
18 five percent of DNA from that total sample is assay for
19 each probe group.

20 And again I think it is important to go
21 through not only how the sample is collected, and how
22 the DNA is extracted, but in assay. HPV PCR assays target
23 a much smaller part of the genom. It allows testing of
24 samples with poor quality DNA.

25 There is some concern that small changes in

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1 the virus either from variants or integration may give
2 false negative results, and the amount of DNA assay
3 varies, and it limits the number of cells that can be
4 sampled.

5 The type specific assays generally target
6 the E-6, E-7 region. That's because their most type
7 variation occurs in this region; whereas, the consensus
8 assays generally target the L-1 region, the area where
9 there is the most conservation.

10 When a consensus assay is used, the types
11 then need to be further determined either based on
12 hybridization, restriction, digest, or actual sequencing
13 of the products.

14 This is just a schematic of one of the
15 currently used PCR assays that relies on a consensus
16 approach, and then a subsequent hybridization. This kind
17 of format, using a line blot approach, allowed for the
18 first time for investigators to look at the presence of
19 multiple types. It wasn't a type specific single
20 approach.

21 In this format beta globin is used as an
22 endogenous positive control for amplifiable DNA, and it
23 is in the process of PCR that the amplicons are actually
24 incorporated into a re-agent that allows it to be
25 detected, and then the hybridization occurs on a filter

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1 strip. And the color indicates which type is present
2 in the assay.

3 Viral quantification is another concern, but
4 at the very base the viral load is very difficult to
5 estimate, because there is uneven tissue distribution
6 of the virus, and there is variation in the kind of
7 sampling.

8 And again because exfoliated cytology is not
9 targeted to the lesion, the sample may or may not include
10 more or less of cells that are actually infected.

11 This requires some measure of the numbers
12 of cells that are actually put into the assay, and most
13 quantitative PCR assays at this point are type specific.

14 Just briefly about in situ hybridizations.

15 It is really the only method that permits
16 directed visualization of the virus in a morphologic
17 context; formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded, and that is
18 routine biopsy tissues can be used.

19 There is reasonable type specificity, but
20 cross-hybridizations, particularly at a high viral copy
21 number, is almost unavoidable, and the results are very
22 technique dependent. It is a very touchy assay.
23 Integration status can be determined on this assay format.

24

25 Serology. Currently the most widely used

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1 is an ELISA-based format, with detection of antibodies
2 that will react with the L-1 ELPs, and these assays have
3 been used on both serum or mucosa samples, looking
4 predominantly at IgG and IgA.

5 The assays are type specific, at least at
6 low titers, and there is some discussion that when there
7 are high titer present whether there is some
8 cross-reactivity between the VLPs.

9 Reaction in this kind of assay format
10 indicates a past or current infection, but longitudinal
11 studies that have followed subjects for acquisition of
12 DNA and then subsequently antibodies have found that 70
13 to 80 percent is sort of the maximum that end up to be
14 positive, and there is a lag time of several months between
15 the acquisition of DNA and the antibody.

16 The L-1 VLP assay formats vary. It can be
17 direct or indirect, and the VLP production is not
18 well-standardized, laboratory to laboratory. There are
19 different expression systems, and there are different
20 ways to prepare this reagent and QC methods need to be
21 developed.

22 In addition, there is really no good gold
23 standard for setting the threshold for positive results,
24 and there are relatively few inter-laboratory
25 comparisons, although they are needed.

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1 So basically I ended with the assays because
2 I think assays are really are a way of understanding the
3 virus, but I want to go back again to the sample, and
4 reemphasize the difference that the varying sample
5 approaches that can be made in the assay.

6 And the amount and how the DNA is extracted,
7 and the amount that is actually put into the assay all
8 will influence results.

9 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much, Dr.
10 Unger. That was a very helpful presentation. If there
11 are a Committee question or two that specifically relate
12 to the factual content of what Dr. Unger said, that's
13 fine, but what I would like to do is get Dr. Wilkinson's
14 presentation under our belt, and then begin reasoning
15 with both of them, and have them see how they impact with
16 the issues that the FDA wishes us to discuss. Dr. Katz.

17 DR. KATZ: In thinking about how a vaccine
18 might work in relation to this virus, I am unclear about
19 how is virus transmitted. You describe a virus that is
20 very tightly associated with this cell.

21 Is it that shedded cells are transmitted to
22 the individual, or are there free virions? What is the
23 mechanism?

24 DR. UNGER: I don't have an answer. It is
25 postulated that the cells are shed in that little packet

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1 of dried epithelium as it sheds, and then presumably the
2 virions get out and get in, and in animal model studies,
3 free virions, that the particles are infectious.

4 DR. KATZ: Thank you.

5 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Drs. Stephens, Pagliusi, and
6 Freedman.

7 DR. STEPHENS: Can you help us understand
8 or at least me understand the pathogenesis of HPV 16,
9 and specifically is that a replication issue, better
10 replication, or is it an ocogene issue? Is it a
11 combination of both? And is there reassortment among
12 papilloma viruses?

13 DR. UNGER: The last question is probably
14 the easiest. There is no evidence of reassociation
15 between the types. Then as far as why HPV 16 is so
16 different from the rest, that relies upon in vitro studies
17 that have shown that the E-6/E-7 proteins do have
18 different propensities to act in an oncogenic fashion
19 in assays.

20 But all of the types have not been studied
21 in great detail, and there could be other factors, such
22 as copy number and amount of the replication.

23 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you. Dr. Pagliusi.

24 DR. PAGLIUSI: I have a comment to your last
25 slide, and so I agree that laboratory diagnostics is a

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1 very important tool, and I just wanted to say that WHO
2 has an effort in this direction, which is in collaboration
3 with the virion particles vaccine developers who are
4 represented here by the NCI, Merck, and GlaxoSmithKline.

5 We are trying to develop some reference
6 reagents to create the tools for the interlaboratory
7 comparisons of results.

8 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you. Dr. Freedman.

9 DR. FREEDMAN: Is there any evidence that
10 an abnormality of the cells making up an epithelium with
11 any degree of transformation that may preexist in the
12 infection, may in fact increase the susceptibility to
13 infection with HPV?

14 I am thinking of the work of Kurofsky a number
15 of years ago, which showed that malignant cells, for
16 example, were more susceptible to infection with a number
17 of viruses.

18 DR. UNGER: I don't know of any studies that
19 would comment on that directly. There is evidence that
20 the dysplastic state of the cell does affect its ability
21 to be sampled in cytology. And as part of the dysplastic
22 process, they also become discohesive, and so the greater
23 degree of dysplasia, the easier it is to kind of scrap
24 it off.

25 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you again, Dr. Unger,

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1 very much. I am sure that we will be calling on you as
2 a resource of information when we move into our
3 discussion. Our next speaker will be Dr. Edward
4 Wilkinson, who will talk about the clinical management
5 and natural history of cervical dysplasia and related
6 findings.

7 DR. WILKINSON: Thank you, Dr. Daum. It is
8 a pleasure and an honor to be here at this very remarkable
9 meeting. Our discussion here is on clinical management,
10 natural history, and I will discuss some aspects of
11 cytopathology, classification, and histopathology
12 classification.

13 I will also show you some examples,
14 colposcopic examples. In the screening data, you have
15 seen much of this, about 50,000 Paps smears a year, and
16 about 3.5 million interpreted as normal, and about 800,000
17 LSILs.

18 And in that subset there is probably about
19 1,600 women who have cervical carcinoma, and about 2,500
20 HSIL groups, which is about at least 2,500 women in that
21 subset that have cervical carcinoma.

22 Now, we recognize that cervical carcinomas
23 primarily arise in the cervical transformation zone,
24 which extends basically from the ectocervical margin of
25 the original squamo-columnar epithelium to the presently

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1 identified squamo-columnar junction.

2 And when one reads the literature, you get
3 sometimes confused at the squamo-columnar junction, and
4 that that is not the transformation zone. It only marks
5 the ectocervical edge of the transformation zone.

6 Now, in the transformation zone, basically
7 what is occurring is the cervix is being remodeled. This
8 occurs with the beginning of adolescence, and actually
9 there is a bit of remodeling in the newborn, and in
10 adolescents there is some major remodeling of the
11 transformation zone.

12 And then after the first child, one normally
13 has a process of reserve cell hyperplasia, XX,
14 and then mature epithelium. As far as the cervical
15 intraepithelial lesions that arise within the
16 transformation zone, the old concept was that this is
17 a continuum, CIN-1, through 2, through 3.

18 And I think that concept has pretty well been
19 disproven, and a bunch of work that I think has been
20 demonstrated today has shown that really CIN-1 is a
21 complex process, and many of these are transient
22 infections.

23 And CIN-2 and 3 are quite a different issue,
24 and CIN-3 for sure is a precursor as far as understanding
25 the process. Now, from the classification from the World

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1 Health Organization, this is a classification of cervical
2 intraepithelial neoplasia.

3 The WHO retains the terminology dysplasia,
4 and so mild dysplasia, CIN-1, and this is a lesion confined
5 to the lowest third of the epithelium. Moderate
6 dysplasia, CIN-2 involves the lower two-thirds of the
7 epithelium.

8 And severe dysplasia extends to the upper
9 third of the epithelium, but not involving full thickness.

10 And this is a CIN-3 lesion, and CIN-3 is also used for
11 carcinoma in situ with full thickness changes.

12 Now, the Bethesda system, although it was
13 first introduced around 1988, and modified in 1991, it
14 has undergone recently the new Bethesda 2001 system, and
15 these are the major issues, although there are a number
16 of others.

17 The term "within normal" has been removed
18 and replaced with "negative for intraepithelial lesion
19 or malignancy." The term "benign cellular changes" has
20 been eliminated. The classification has actually been
21 eliminated.

22 And the interpretation of AGUS has been
23 changed to atypical squamos cells, and this can be either
24 atypical squamos cells of uncertain significance, or
25 undetermined significance, and atypical squamos cells

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1 cannot exclude a high grade lesion.

2 And finally atypical glandular cells, and
3 AGUS has been changed to atypical glandular cells, and
4 this has been primarily to eliminate the confusion between
5 AGUS and ASCUS, which many people confuse much to the
6 negative impact of the patient.

7 Now, the new terminology is here in all of
8 these slides, and I have these in your syllabus materials.

9 So basically we have the negative category, and then
10 we have an epithelial cell abnormality squamos cell.

11 And this includes atypical squamos cells
12 ASCUS and ASCH, and then low grade, cervical
13 intraepithelial lesion, and high grade cervical
14 intraepithelial lesion; and finally squamous cell
15 carcinoma.

16 Now, this is an example of a low grade
17 cytology, and atypical colas site with the distinct
18 paranuclear halo, and the nuclear outline is somewhat
19 irregular, and the chromatin is somewhat abnormal, and
20 the cell is approximately three times the diameter of
21 the normal intermediate squamous cell.

22 This is a colposcopic view of a patient with
23 a low grade lesion, and this reddish blush, you can see
24 the lesion here, although there is no other abnormality.

25

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1 Her transformation only extends from here
2 out to the areas where we can see some of the original
3 squamous epithelial, and here are the cysts, and so you
4 can see all of this is the transformation zone, and this
5 lesion is well within the transformation zone.

6 And with a little lugol solution one can see
7 the intraepithelial lesion does not stain with iodine,
8 and it does not contain glycogen, like the normal glycogen
9 rich ectocervical epithelium, and squamous mature
10 metaplasia epithelium will stain with the glycogen.

11 So this is a CIN-1 lesion in the cervical
12 transformation zone of at risk woman. This is the biopsy
13 showing this parabasalar proliferation with disordered
14 epithelium in the lower third. There are also the corlow
15 (phonetic) sites that we expect to see in the typical
16 low grade or mild dysplasia lesion.

17 For the purposes of this presentation, I will
18 use World Health Organization terminology for histology,
19 namely CIN-1, 2, or 3 values, and Bethesda terminology
20 for cytology; low grade, high grade, and such. So this
21 is a CIN-1 lesion, typical HPV changes.

22 Now, the cytology of a high grade lesion shows
23 larger nuclide, and usually with less cytoplasm, and in
24 this case there is a moderate amount of cytoplasm, and
25 the nuclear chromatin is coarse, and what has been

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1 referred to as salt and pepper type pattern outlines are
2 somewhat irregular.

3 And these cells are relatively large. For
4 example, here is a PMN in comparison. These cells reflect
5 a higher grade lesion. Now, this is a colposcopic photo,
6 and I hope that you can see this, but this is a very small
7 lesion on the anterior lip of a Paris woman.

8 This lesion, and you can appreciate the small
9 size, but this slide was provided to me by Dr. Darren
10 Ferris. I think one of the important things about high
11 grade lesions is they can be very small.

12 In fact, I think many times when one looks
13 at statistics on mild dysplasia CIN-1, the low grade Paps
14 smears, that in fact about 15 percent are high grade harbor
15 or reflect high grade lesions.

16 And I think it is this kind of a lesion. This
17 is a high grade lesion, and it has mosaic, and it has
18 punctuation. It is on the anterior lip and it is in the
19 transformation zone, but it is a very small lesion.

20 This can give you some idea. This is the
21 cervical os here, and so this is very close magnification,
22 and there is a very small lesion on the anterior lip of
23 the cervix in the transformation zone.

24 This is the histology of a high grade lesion,
25 and this would be classified as a CIN-2 lesion and the

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1 changes are in the upper two-thirds, but there are still
2 nice corlosites, and usually the more severe the lesion
3 the less probability that you will see corlosites.

4 There is also abnormal eidetic activity and
5 lots of nuclear disarray. In the very high grade lesion
6 one will see again the chromotine features of the
7 intraepithelium neoplastic lesion, and in this case there
8 is very minimum cytoplasm.

9 These cells have marked foldings in
10 irregularity, and are rather characteristic of a high
11 grade lesion, and in this case, a carcinoma in situ, CIN-3
12 lesion.

13 And here is the colposcopy as such an example,
14 but the cervical os now is here, and this is the vagina
15 anterior, and this is a very large lesion, extending over
16 most of the anterior transformation zone, and with the
17 3 percent acetic acid application, one can appreciate
18 those extensive mosaic pattern in this lesion.

19 This is a very high grade lesion and very
20 large lesion. This is a biopsy of an example of a
21 carcinoma in situ, CIN-3 lesion, and here you will see
22 no maturation. The cells here show total
23 disorganization, and with actually a vertical
24 orientation, and there is abnormal mitotic activity, and
25 this is CIN-3 carcinoma in situ.

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1 Now, finally, squamous carcinoma on cytology
2 is reflected in this sort of picture, where one sees sheets
3 and groupings of cells. The cells, unlike the high grade
4 CIN, do contain substantial amount of cytoplasm, and often
5 have small nuclei, and are in groupings as you see here.

6
7 This is a rather typical picture of a squamous
8 carcinoma of the non-keratinizing type, which is the usual
9 variety, and this is a colposcopic examination of a
10 patient that has an early invasive carcinoma.

11 Now, this patient has extensive CIN-3, with
12 lots of mosaic pattern, in this anterior cervix. This
13 is the cervical os, just to be oriented here, and the
14 cervix is quite large as you can appreciate.

15 But this is a high grade lesion here, a CIN-3
16 lesion here in this location, but here we have abnormal
17 hair pin type vessels, characteristic of early invasion,
18 or superficial invasion, early carcinoma in a field of
19 carcinoma or CIN-3.

20 Here is the biopsy showing a CIN-3 lesion,
21 and the invasive tumor here. This tumor is relatively
22 small actually. It was under three millimeters in depth,
23 and less than seven millimeters in length. So it would
24 be a Stage 1-A Sub-1.

25 But this is an evasive squamous cell

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1 carcinoma, and here is the invasive tumor in the stroma,
2 with the adjacent CIN-3 lesion. Most of the early
3 invasion carcinomas that are seen do have adjacent high
4 grade CIN-3 lesion.

5 Now, in addition to the squamous lesions,
6 we should talk a bit about the glandular lesions. These
7 are also HPV related. In the Bethesda system, this is
8 considered epithelial so abnormality glandular. These
9 can be atypical of endocervical and endometrial, or
10 glandular, or otherwise specified.

11 Or they can reflect endocervical or
12 adenocarcinoma in situ, or be obvious adenocarcinoma,
13 or endocervical, or endometrial, or extrauterine
14 location. Now, this is an example of atypical glandular
15 pap test from a young woman, a 32 year old woman.

16 And this reflects adenocarcinoma in situ in
17 the cervical cytology, and there the cells are crowded
18 together, and these cells have small nuclei, but also
19 have this feathering characteristics that are descriptive
20 of glandular lesions.

21 This patient in addition had a few of these
22 very large cells with huge prominent nuclei, and this
23 is an example of the background of carcinoma in situ.
24 This is the appearance of her cervix, and here her
25 transformation zone in fact is normal from this glandular

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1 cone rejunction out and everything is normal.

2 In fact, some early work, you could not
3 recognize glandular in situ lesions. However, Dr. Cecil
4 Wright and Michael Shire have recently published a book
5 on recognition of adenocarcinoma in situ lesions.

6 They occur in the endocervical epithelium,
7 and approximal if you would to the glandular
8 squamo-columnar junction, and these lesions are sometimes
9 characterized by the yellow color or red color that one
10 encounters in the endocervical epithelium, and often
11 quite adjacent to the columnar epithelium at the
12 squamo-columnar junction.

13 Here is normal columnar mucous epithelium
14 of the endocervix and here is the adenocarcinoma in situ,
15 and here the cells are similar to those that we saw in
16 the cytology. Glands are crowded together, but there
17 is no invasion. This is a typical adenocarcinoma in situ
18 of the endocervix.

19 Now, when one compares the WHO terminology
20 for histopathology, and the Bethesda system terminology
21 for cytology, there is correlation in the sense that a
22 mild dysplasia or CIN-1 is LSIL, and then CIN-2 and CIN-3
23 are all HSIL.

24 So there is maybe of use when one compares
25 these terminologies. So when one looks for correlation,

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1 you would like to have an LSIL pap smear reflect a CIN-1
2 lesion on biopsy, for example.

3 Now, there are lots of reasons for lack of
4 correlation between cytology and colposcopy, and this
5 is really a partial list. Most of the problems in my
6 opinion are related to a sampling, and either the biopsy
7 site is not good, or the cytology sample is not what it
8 might be, but this is of ongoing interest to
9 cytopathologists and pathologists interested in disease
10 of the cervix, to achieve the best possible diagnosis,
11 both cytologically and by biopsy based on proper
12 collection of the sample, and processing of the sample,
13 and interpretation.

14 Now, let's look at some of these Bethesda
15 classifications in cytology and in association with CIN.

16 ASCUS is the atypical squamous cells, and average
17 frequency the College of American Pathologist reports
18 across the United States frequency is about 4.4 percent
19 of all Pap tests.

20 Associated CIN-2/3 in these patients when
21 one does colposcopy and biopsy, between 5 to 17 percent,
22 and the association of ASCUS with cervical carcinoma,
23 somewhere around a tenth to 2/10ths of one percent.

24 Now, the sensitivity of a single pap test
25 for the detection of CIN-2/3 is probably not especially

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1 good. Somewhere around .67 to .76, and there is a number
2 of studies that have looked at this, including studies
3 from the National Cancer Institute.

4 Now, if you look at the ALTS trial and ASCUS
5 cytology, looking at a review of the cytology findings,
6 where there was concurrence by the quality assurance
7 committee of 55 percent, and upgraded to LSIL, 11 percent;
8 and upgraded to HSIL, 3 percent.

9 So about 14 percent then were considered SIL
10 rather than ASCUS, but downgraded to negative, 31 percent,
11 as compared to the peripheral centers, and this correlated
12 pretty well with the HPV testing that was done in this
13 subset also.

14 I think there is an important point in the
15 Bethesda system. There is a discussion about ancillary
16 testing for ASCUS and these are the high risk subsets
17 that have been reported, and high risk testing does tend
18 to focus on the 13 high risk subsites, and probably most
19 importantly the 16, 18, 45, and 56 being the ones that
20 are the most prevalent and associated with carcinoma.

21 Now, HPV testing has been looked at as adjunct
22 to cervical cytology and cancer cervical screening, and
23 it has great promise as far as sensitivity goes. This
24 is comparing HPV testing sensitivity with cervical
25 cytology, accepting ASCUS or higher as the threshold for

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1 action, and specificity is here, but referral to a
2 colposcopy is also included.

3 So this is pretty good evidence of long
4 sensitivity to HPV testing, and this is some independent
5 work and not NCI-based data looking, and looking at HPV
6 positive.

7 And one thing to point out is that LSIL has
8 a high frequency of HPV positivity in most studies, 69
9 percent or higher, and 85 percent in some series. Also,
10 high grade SIL has high HPV frequency.

11 So the use of HPV testing is not recommended
12 in adjuncts as far as LSIL or HSIL in the initial
13 evaluation process. Normal patients here, 30 percent,
14 were referred to as HPV positive.

15 Now, comparing a number of studies, and this
16 is some work that -- this is a partial listing from work
17 that Tom Wright and myself, and Tom Cox, and Leo Twiggs,
18 are working on as a report. This will be the cytology
19 report from the 2001 consensus conference sponsored by
20 the American Society for the Study of Colposcopy.

21 And this work is still basically in present
22 embargo because this work has been submitted, but I will
23 share this with you; that the sensitivity management of
24 ASCUS, the sensitivity of HPV DNA testing in these four
25 studies cited is excellent.

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1 And when one compares it to cytology, it is
2 certainly comparable, and in some cases better than a
3 repeat cytology. So that the HPV testing I think has
4 earned a place in the clinical management in dealing with
5 patients with ASCUS.

6 Now, this is work again from the NCI ALTS
7 study, and again looking at the HPV predictive value,
8 and negative predictive value, and I think the most
9 important thing here is this high value for the negative
10 predictive value of hybrid capture testing in this study
11 mode.

12 And this is both for CIN-3, as well as CIN-2,
13 and the negative protective value was very high with HPV
14 testing. The positive predictive value is relatively
15 low. Now, ASCUS cannot exclude high grade SIL, or
16 ASCUS-H.

17 In this case, the association with CIN-2 or
18 3, if you look at ASCUS overall, it is about 5 to 17
19 percent. But if you look at ASCUS to favor a high grade
20 lesion or cannot exclude a high grade lesion, the
21 association with CIN-2/3 is 24 to 94 percent.

22 And as a result, in this ASCUS favor high
23 grade, there does not appear to be a use for HPV testing.

24 Rather, a referral directly to a colposcopy is a prudent
25 act as far as clinical management in that setting.

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1 Now, how is the use of HPV triage for the
2 ASCUS U.S. pap test. This is a model that has been
3 discussed in a number of papers. Basically, a patient
4 has an ASCUS U.S. pap test result, and what is the next
5 step.

6 One strategy would be to do HPV testing, and
7 if the HPV test shows a high risk HPV type, the patient
8 then could be referred to a colposcopy and evaluation;
9 or return for repeat cytology, with follow-up on a regular
10 basis, with the understanding that if a pap is again ASCUS
11 or more severe, that colposcopy would occur.

12 The other strategy if the patient is HPV
13 negative would be then just to return the patient to return
14 paps smear testing in 12 months. So, HPV testing could
15 be used in that method to reduce the reduced colposcopy
16 and evaluation of that type.

17 Now, looking at management of ASCUS, U.S.
18 acceptable options could be follow the patient with repeat
19 cytology in 6 and 12 months; if ASCUS or more severe
20 lesion, refer to a colposcopy.

21 And the next option would be to perform HPV
22 DNA testing for risk types. If the patient is negative,
23 return to screening. If positive, repeat the cervical
24 cytology in 6 to 12 months; and if more severe, then refer
25 to colposcopy. If ASCUS or more severe, refer to

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1 colposcopy.

2 And there may be a use here for HPV testing
3 and this will be discussed in the consensus conference,
4 but it looks like these patients, if they are persistent
5 HPV added at 12 months, that then one needs to pursue
6 them as Dr. Schiffman discussed earlier today.

7 LSIL frequency in association with CIN. The
8 mean frequency of LSIL across the U.S. is about 1.6 percent
9 of all the pap tests that are done. Associated CIN or
10 CIN-2/3 is around 15 to 30 percent. And as I said, many
11 people are of the opinion that these are probably not
12 new CIN-3s that have evolved from the CIN-1.

13 They rather represent a subset of CIN-2/3
14 lesions that in fact did not shed enough cells, or were
15 not interpreted as CIN-2/3 on the initial evaluation.

16 LSIL associated with cervical carcinoma is
17 quite low, under .1 percent. Now, follow-up observations
18 versus therapy, about 70 percent in a study here by a
19 large study by the University of Florida, and 70 percent
20 of our patients with LSIL pap had colposcopic follow-up
21 and were found to have a lesion.

22 And 47 percent of these had CIN-1, and 28.4
23 percent had CIN-2/3. So it has generally been our
24 practice at the University of Florida to follow patients
25 with colposcopy that have LSIL paps, and I think that

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1 is pretty much a rule in the United States in most
2 settings.

3 So the options then would be to refer directly
4 to colposcopy, recognizing that these patients often will
5 have something. If the biopsies fail to identify CIN,
6 then one has the option to follow with cytology at 6 and
7 12 months, or to refer to a colposcopy at that point if
8 the pap is ASCUS U.S. or more severe.

9 Another option would be to follow with a pap
10 in 6 and 12 months, with referral in special
11 circumstances, such as pregnant women, or adolescents,
12 or patients where a colposcopy may not be necessarily
13 needed in certain situations.

14 Now, HSIL frequency in association with CIN.
15 The mean frequency of HSIL and cervical cytology in the
16 U.S. is about 0.45 percent, and associated with CIN-2/3
17 is fairly high. It is about 70 to 75 percent in most
18 laboratories.

19 HSIL associated with cervical carcinoma is
20 about 1 to 2 percent, and that is on the initial
21 evaluation. So this is a very productive group of
22 patients to pursue as far as finding significant disease,
23 and finding invasive carcinoma.

24 Now, with HSIL recommendations are to refer
25 directly to colposcopy, and if lesions are identified,

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1 then biopsies and appropriate endocervical evaluation,
2 and so forth.

3 However, if colposcopy and biopies fail to
4 identify CIN, then the recommendation is to review the
5 original cytology, biopsies and colposcopy findings to
6 figure out what exactly was identified.

7 If the review confirms HSIL, then a
8 diagnostic excisional procedure, such as an electro-loop
9 excision of the transformation zone is recommended in
10 non-pregnant patients.

11 And as I said, this is a situation where there
12 could be a significant lesion and some of these HSIL
13 lesions are in fact quite small, and difficult to
14 identify.

15 Now, HPV results by hybrid capture looking
16 at the various subsets, and this is NCI data again, that
17 you will notice that the ASCUS, in about half of the cases,
18 47 percent, were negative, and 48.9 percent positive.

19 In LSIL, a very high frequency of HPV testing,
20 and NIH's ALT trial data has also shown that HPV testing
21 in the front end of evaluation of patients with LSIL or
22 HSIL is not of value in the assessment of a lesion.

23 Now, high risk HPV detection, we know that
24 using the standard methods that are used, in the study
25 from Dr. Wright, that women with CIN-2/3 disease, HPV

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1 will be detected in about 83.9 percent, but probably most
2 of those lesions are HPV positive if one could study them
3 in other ways.

4 Women with no disease though, about 15
5 percent, have HPV detected in many settings. Now, what
6 is the risk of high grade CIN in relation to time since
7 first exposure to HPV 16. This is very difficult
8 information to try to come about.

9 Dr. Laura Koutsky has got some data, where
10 she had some patients that actually presented within 24
11 months of exposure. This is Dr. Woodman's data showing
12 that there were some that presented as early as 6 months,
13 and some at 12 to 18 months, and even a few presenting
14 beyond 18 months.

15 But you can see that the majority of the
16 patients did present within 6 to 18 months for certain
17 as far if they were to develop a lesion. Now, pap test
18 results preceding the identification of women with
19 CIN-2/3, and I think it is interesting that when one is
20 looking for CIN-2/3, if that is what we specifically need
21 to find, which I think is very important, to be able to
22 identify.

23 And about 31 percent in fact of the total
24 cases are recognized initially on paps smear, or related
25 to the paps smear test. LSIL is about 15 to 30 percent

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1 of LSIL paps harbor high grade or harbor CIN-2/3 lesions.

2 Interestingly, of the atypical glandular
3 cell group, around 30 to 40 percent of those patients
4 harbor CIN-2/3, and with the CIN-2/3 presenting
5 cytologically as an atypical glandular cell fissure.

6 And among the atypical squamous cell
7 category, or ASCUS category, about 10 percent of those
8 patients will have high grade lesions in the general
9 setting.

10 So when we look for high grade lesion, or
11 if we are trying to find CIN-2/3, we need to look at all
12 four of these subsets of cytologic findings if we are
13 going to find all the patients that in fact have CIN-2/3.

14 Now, let's look at the atypical glandular
15 cell issue, and the frequency of association with CIN,
16 and adenocarcinoma in situ are in the mutual
17 adenocarcinoma. The mean frequency is quite low, about
18 0.3 percent.

19 Depending on the study that you look at, the
20 frequency of CIN-1, 2, or 3 is between 9 to 54 percent
21 in this group. So even though the cytology findings imply
22 glandular abnormality, many of these patients in fact
23 have a squamous abnormality.

24 Adenocarcinoma in situ is a fairly important
25 lesion, up to 8 percent in some series, and with atypical

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1 glandular cells with associated carcinoma, 1 to 9 percent.

2 And among those carcinomas are included endometrial
3 endocarcinomas, and not just any cervical endocarcinomas.

4 Now, atypical glandular cells associated
5 with CIN-2 or 3, atypical glandular cells not otherwise
6 specified, CIN-2/3 detected was between 9 to 41 percent,
7 given the given series.

8 And atypical glandular cells favor
9 neoplasia, which is another subcategory in the new
10 Bethesda system, CIN-2/3 detected 27 to 96 percent. So
11 atypical glandular cells are a very important observation
12 and if a pathologist favors neoplasia in the
13 interpretation, there is a very good possibility that
14 there is either a glandular or squamous lesion in that
15 particular patient.

16 I would point out that cervical
17 adenocarcinomas are also associated with 16 and 18, and
18 this is just one study looking at a series of 38 cases,
19 and 60.5 percent HPV detected, and 16 detected in 23
20 percent, and 18, 26 percent, and in the patients that
21 were 59 years of age or younger, 84.6 percent had
22 detectable HPV in their adenocarcinoma.

23 So, adenocervical adenocarcinoma and
24 adenocarcinoma in situ is one other neoplasia lesion of
25 the cervix related to and associated with a human

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1 papilloma virus, especially 16 and 18.

2 Now, management of atypical glandular cells,
3 this is a somewhat complex issue. We know that we need
4 to do colposcopy because there is a lot of high grade
5 or HSIL CIN lesions among those looking like glandular
6 lesions.

7 It should include an evaluation of the
8 adenocervix, and in symptomatic women, and women over
9 35 years of age, the ASCCP consensus conference, the
10 concept was that adenometrial samplings should also be
11 performed, and I think other papers have supported that
12 very well.

13 Now, a diagnostic cervical cone biopsy may
14 be needed in these patients and if that is the situation
15 where glandular lesion or a lesion cannot be identified
16 in the face of atypical glandular cells, these patients
17 need to have an expert clinical opinion and an experienced
18 clinician evaluate them because of the risk of associated
19 glandular or CIN-3 associated lesion.

20 Now, natural history issues are difficult
21 to fully understand, and I think it is confused a bit
22 because of sampling issues and other matters. But this
23 is just a literature analysis that Dr. Andrew Ostor did.
24 He is quite good at these sort of things.

25 And he did look at CIN-1, 2 and 3, and in

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1 his analysis of a little over 4,500 cases, looking at
2 17 studies, ranging from 12 to 1,269 cases, 57 percent
3 regressed; and 32 percent persisted; and 11 percent
4 progressed to a higher grade CIN or CIS.

5 And looking at the CIN-2 lesions, their
6 history based on the historical review of these papers,
7 regression, 43 percent, persistence, 35 percent, and
8 progression to carcinoma in situ, CIN-3, was 22 percent
9 in that subset.

10 And looking at the CIS or CIN-3 subset,
11 including severe dysplasia, he had a total range of
12 studies from -- 21 studies, ranging from 5 to 109 patients
13 in the study, and 32 regressed or 30 percent regressed;
14 and 56 percent persisted, and 12 percent progressed to
15 invasion.

16 Now, I must say that I think that when one
17 looks at some of these studies, it is really hard to
18 understand regression in CIN-3, and I think that maybe
19 there is need of some further discussion about that, but
20 I think there is reason to seriously question if a true
21 carcinoma in situ CIN-3 lesion will ever regress. So
22 I think there are some issues that need to be looked at
23 there.

24 Overall then looking at persistence at CIN-1,
25 CIN-2, and CIN-3, progression to higher grade CIN, low

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1 in CIN-1, 22 percent CIN-2; and progression to invasion,
2 the studies would support that CIN-3 is the biggest issue,
3 but some CIN-2 lesions are also reported.

4 They are rare in CIN-1, and this may in fact
5 represent sampling issues that we don't fully understand.

6 Now, when one looks at the cytology issues, and this
7 is in studies done by Dr. Melnikow, looking at the --
8 this is a meta analysis looking at regression in cytology
9 issues, and looking at the range, ASCUS, you can see the
10 fairly common regression of ASCUS cytology, and low grade
11 SIL cytology regression from 40 to 60 percent roughly.

12 ASCUS with low grade is similar, and then
13 high grade SIL, some regression here, 20 to a little over
14 50 percent in cytology regression. But of course
15 cytology regression, one is always facing issues of
16 sampling also.

17 Progression, ASCUS, about a little over 10
18 percent progression, and this is interesting comparing
19 six months follow-up to 24 months follow-up. So you had
20 6 months follow-up fairly low, but there are some cases
21 here having progression in the ASCUS subset; and in low
22 grade lesions, the range is quite variable.

23 You can see from about 7 percent and all the
24 way up to almost 35 percent of progression in these low
25 grade subset of cytology. We would expect in any low

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1 grade subset that we would see about 15 percent with
2 CIN-2/3 eventually being manifest.

3 And then in looking at high grade cases, there
4 was some recognition of regression by cytology in these
5 cases also, or in progression, and you can see the
6 progression rate here again, the 3 month progression rate
7 versus 24 months, and there is quite a significant
8 difference.

9 And then finally invasive carcinoma, which
10 is a fairly typical marker, you are looking at ASCUS,
11 and this is 6 months and 24 months follow-up, and you
12 can see some invasive carcinoma cases are found in the
13 ASCUS subset or cytology, and basic carcinoma infrequent
14 finding in low grade lesions, .5 percent here.

15 ASCUS low grade SIL, again low, and high grade
16 SIL is up to 4 percent here, and one of the high rates
17 in this subset. Now, management of CIN-1, some of the
18 issues that we need to consider and these have been
19 summarized by Dr. Howard Jones very nicely in this study,
20 basic cancer may already exist in the case of CIN-1.

21 We know that CIN-2 or 3 can exist in some
22 cases; and invasive cancer develops between follow-up
23 visits; or patients are lost to follow-up and develops
24 invasive cancer.

25 And so we choose to follow CIN-1 lesions,

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1 and we have to recognize that situation. Here is a study
2 from Dr. Shafi, from the British Journal of OB-GYN,
3 looking at a LSIL atypious situation, and immediate LLETZ
4 for 24 months.

5 And of those that had immediate LLETZ, he
6 found CIN-2/3 in 23 percent, and what is interesting is
7 that those that he followed for 24 months and then
8 evaluated, he had 24 percent.

9 And this observation of CIN-3 in these
10 follow-up studies has also been supported in the ALTS
11 trial, where you see the CIN-2/3 subset emerging from
12 cases initially interpreted as CIN-1. So this probably
13 represents a small subset, maybe a quarter of those cases
14 where we don't recognize the CIN-3 lesion or CIN-2 lesion
15 in the face of a apparent CIN-1 case.

16 Now, these are some ACOG committee opinions
17 that have been stated and published, and there are authors
18 who have contributed, such as Drs. Gold and Ferris, for
19 example.

20 But here is some observational follow-up of
21 CIN-1 that has been recommended to clinicians, and if
22 the patient has a follow-up paps smear that is within
23 normal or benign cellular changes, repeat follow-up at
24 4 to 6 month intervals should continue.

25 If the smears remain normal, or benign, a

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1 patient may return to annual screening after four
2 consecutive normal or unremarkable pap tests. On the
3 other hand, if any of these return as ASCUS or LSIL, or
4 HSIL, the patient should then be referred to colposcopy,
5 with directed biopsies and this is very important in the
6 evaluation of these patients, recognizing the possibility
7 of underlying CIN-2/3 or invasive tumor.

8 Now, the treatment or decision on such
9 patients is dependent upon pathologic findings.
10 Patients that have CIN-2/3 require appropriate treatment
11 for cervical endometrial neoplasia. However, patients
12 with CIN-1 may have observational follow-up if that is
13 acceptable to the physician and the patient.

14 Treatment versus observation. Grossly
15 visible lesions of the cervix require a biopsy and this
16 is very important. Cytology can miss even if we see a
17 lesion. Grossly visible CIN-2 or 3 lesions may be
18 associated with invasive carcinoma, and usually a micro
19 invasion or rarely adenocarcinoma in situ or invasive
20 adenocarcinoma.

21 And importantly the approach using
22 electro-loop excision of any visible lesion is generally
23 not recommended due to common treatment of non-CIN lesions
24 over treatment basically, but biopsy of course is
25 necessary for appropriate diagnosis.

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1 Outcomes. Systemic review of controlled and
2 randomized trials in connection with CIN-1, and CIN-2,
3 and outcomes as far as recurrence of CIN-1 or occurrence
4 of CIN or non-recurrence of CIN between cone biopsy,
5 cryotherapy, laser ablation, electro-loop excision,
6 demonstrated no substantial differences in outcome as
7 described by Dr. Norvelle in a meta-analysis of treatment
8 outcomes.

9 Methods of treatment. These are the most
10 common used in the United States. I would say that
11 electro-loop excision is probably the most common right
12 now used for low grade lesions that are treated in the
13 outpatient setting.

14 Laser ablation is of less common use, and
15 cryosurgery is still used for low grade lesions in some
16 settings. You can see that depending on the method of
17 treatment the complication rate related to hemorrhage
18 is highly variable, but electro-loop excision is
19 generally well tolerated in most settings.

20 Residual CIN after loop excision is an issue,
21 and if margins are involved, or if the ECC contains CIN,
22 there can be persistent disease in as many as 48 to 59
23 percent of the cases, even though they undergo LEEP
24 incisions.

25 So doing electro-loop excision is not the

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1 whole answer. We have to recognize that in the management
2 of CIN lesions that ablative therapy is not recommended
3 for squamo-columnar injunction when limits of lesions
4 are not identified.

5 A negative ECC prior to ablative therapy is
6 suggested by most experts. ECC at the time of loop
7 excision may indicate an increased risk of residual
8 disease, but may not influence post-LEEP management, and
9 a CIN-3 approach for low-grade lesions tends to result
10 in excessive types of surgery and results in negative
11 histology.

12 And with that, I will stop, and we will open
13 it up for questions. Thank you.

14 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much, Dr.
15 Wilkinson. What I would like to do again is ask the
16 committee members for questions of clarifying data or
17 issues directly related to the factual content of Dr.
18 Wilkinson's presentation.

19 Well, I have one that I would like to ask
20 actually. Can you put in perspective maybe in just a
21 few clarifying comments, and I know it was all in that
22 talk, but the difference between CIN-2 and 3?

23 I have seen data today where they are lumped,
24 and data today where they are separated, and could you
25 just comment on that?

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1 DR. WILKINSON: Well, the WHO has defined
2 this as a CIN-2 lesion, and the abnormalities may extend
3 up to the two-thirds edge of the epithelium. If you would
4 grade the epithelium as one-third, two-thirds, and top,
5 and so a CIN-2 lesion could be called -- the
6 adenoepithelial cell abnormalities could extend all the
7 way to the two-thirds edge, but not beyond that.

8 With the CIN-3 lesion, the abnormalities,
9 the cellular abnormalities would extend beyond that.
10 Now, this is sometimes a bit arbitrary, because you have
11 cordocytotic changes and other features, but I think for
12 most pathologists the grading of CIN-2 and CIN-3 is fairly
13 consistent.

14 In fact, the higher the grade of the CIN,
15 the more reliable the grading becomes.

16 CHAIRMAN DAUM: So in your mind, most of the
17 time you are a splitter, and that there are two distinct
18 pathologic entities here?

19 DR. WILKINSON: Yes. I think most -- there
20 is a trend among pathologists to try to lump them together,
21 and I think that -- for example, most pathologists would
22 prefer not to call carcinoma in situ because it has certain
23 implications, but there are cases that clearly fit the
24 definition of carcinoma in situ as I showed you here.

25 We have full thickness change without any

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1 surface maturation. But I think in general that is in
2 a poll across the United States, but I think that most
3 pathologists still separate out CIN-1, 2, and 3.

4 CHAIRMAN DAUM: I have one more question
5 actually, and that is that official bodies that impinge
6 or set a standard if you will for clinical practice, and
7 I am trying to choose my words carefully -- like ACOG,
8 for example.

9 DR. WILKINSON: American College of OB-GYN,
10 yes.

11 CHAIRMAN DAUM: I gather from your comments
12 that they have now established clinical definitions of
13 persistence of HPV infection, and if that is the case,
14 can you just say exactly what they are?

15 DR. WILKINSON: I am not certain. The
16 American College of OB-GYN has done that. Dr. Zinberg
17 and his committee, clinical practice committee, have been
18 looking at that very carefully, and also looking at the
19 issues of HPV testing, and its applications.

20 And I think they are still considering that
21 situation very carefully, but I don't think they have
22 made a formal statement that I am aware of about what
23 the definition of persistent HPV is.

24 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Are they about to or do you
25 know?

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1 DR. WILKINSON: I think they are very
2 interested in it, the clinical practice committee is,
3 and you could probably contact Dr. Zinberg and he would
4 be glad to discuss -- Dr. Stanley Zinberg at the ACOG,
5 and I am sure that he would be glad to discuss that with
6 you.

7 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Well, it may have an impact
8 on some of the things that we are deliberating, and that's
9 why I am sort of curious to hear your opinion.

10 DR. SNIDER: If I could just follow up on
11 the first question you asked. I understand that from
12 a particular specimen that there are -- that there would
13 be a reasonable expectation that you could differentiate
14 CIN-2 from CIN-3.

15 I wonder though how that really represents
16 what is going on in the patient, because you showed us,
17 for example, a patient who had invasive cancer, but then
18 at another site had -- I guess it would be CIN-3.

19 DR. WILKINSON: CIN-3, right.

20 DR. SNIDER: So would the same kind of thing
21 be expected to occur in a fairly high proportion of
22 patients, where at one site you might get CIN-2, and at
23 another CIN-3?

24 DR. WILKINSON: I think that may occur, and
25 as a matter of fact, the lesions that occur closer to

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1 the squamo-columnar junction tend to be the higher grade
2 lesions.

3 And skilled colposcopists have learned to
4 identify these more significant lesions in the field of
5 CIN on colposcopy findings. But we are as pathologists
6 extremely dependent upon the clinician's ability to
7 biopsy a specific area or areas, and that is one of the
8 potential variables in the correlation between cytology
9 and biopsy findings.

10 And not only cytologic sampling, but also
11 biopsy sampling. But this is true in all fields of biopsy
12 as you know, and I think that has been one of the issues
13 with the interest in the electro-loop excision device,
14 because with that they can excise the entire
15 transformation zone, and not have to deal with that
16 problem.

17 The trouble is that the poor patient ends
18 up with a lot of cervix being removed that doesn't need
19 to be removed. But that is a very important issue;
20 accurate biopsies or multi-biopsies.

21 And I would just add that some physicians
22 are under the misunderstanding that a patient is charged
23 for every biopsy separately, but by pathology standards
24 of billing, if the biopsies are all placed in the same
25 container, because it is a contiguous site, it is only

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1 one bill.

2 But if they make an effort to clearly define
3 different sites, there will be a different bill for every
4 site.

5 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Are there other committee
6 questions of Dr. Wilkinson? Okay. The next item that
7 I guess -- and thank you very much, Dr. Wilkinson. That
8 was very helpful. Dr. Goldenthal, do you want to say
9 some words now to us about -- you are on the program here
10 for reintroduction of questions.

11 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, this is when I was
12 going to give a 30 minute presentation on endpoints.

13 CHAIRMAN DAUM: That would be wonderful.
14 Would you now do that. Thank you. I couldn't tell for
15 sure.

16 (Brief Pause.)

17 CHAIRMAN DAUM: I am going to yield from
18 dissent from the committee here. Dr. Goldenthal needs
19 a few minutes to set up, and I apologize for this. We
20 will take a short break. We will break until 3:30, and
21 then Dr. Goldenthal will begin her presentation at 3:30.

22 (Whereupon, the conference was recessed at
23 3:20 p.m., and resumed at 3:32 p.m.)

24 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Could we have everybody
25 settle down and take their seats, please. During the

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1 break people have come up to me to ask about this business
2 of ACOG's view of persistent infection, and I have tried
3 to persuade some of them to say a word in public here,
4 and so I will call on Dr. O'Connor briefly, and then Dr.
5 Freedman to say one or two sentences about clarifying
6 the question that I asked. Dr. O'Connor.

7 DR. O'CONNOR: One or two sentences, and the
8 best thing that I can say is guidelines are forthcoming.

9 I am not purporting to speak as a spokesperson for ACOG,
10 but much of what has been presented here is information
11 that has happened very recently.

12 You are talking about just within the past
13 year, and changes in the cytology reporting with the
14 Bethesda system, and then the American Society for
15 Colposcopy and Cervical Pathology Conference in
16 September, all of these things are to be published, and
17 you can expect from that that parent societies such as
18 ACOG, and the American Academy of Family Practice, will
19 come out with endorsements, guidelines that would reflect
20 the information that is presently to be published.

21 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much. Dr.
22 Freedman.

23 DR. FREEDMAN: The only thing that I can add
24 is that it is obvious when you see the data that the lack
25 of standardization of approaches to some of these lesions,

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1 like ASCUS and CIN, really is demanded some type of
2 standardization.

3 And that is what is forthcoming, and I think
4 it should be helpful at least in perhaps having fewer
5 people undergo a procedure that they don't really need.

6 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Okay. Thank you very much,
7 both of you, for your clarification, and we will try one
8 more time to get Dr. Goldenthal's talk under way. Dr.
9 Goldenthal.

10 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Thank you. I would like
11 to take this opportunity to give you FDA's perspective
12 on HPV preventive vaccine endpoints. But first I would
13 like to acknowledge some FDA staff who have served as
14 clinical primary reviewers on the various HPV vaccine
15 files, as well as staff who assisted in the preparation
16 of the two briefing documents.

17 Worldwide, cervical cancer is the third most
18 common cause of cancer in women. In developing
19 countries, it is the second most common cause, and in
20 developed countries, it is the sixth most common cause
21 of cancer in women.

22 Worldwide, there are an estimated 400,000
23 to 500,000 new cases per year, and of interest is that
24 there has been a disturbing trend in one developed
25 country, which is where an increase in actually instances

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1 of cervical cancer has been observed for women under 55
2 years of age.

3 And worldwide for cervical cancer there are
4 approximately 190,000 deaths per year, and 78 percent
5 of which occur in developing countries. Now, looking
6 at it from the U.S. perspective, in the 1930s, cervical
7 cancer was the most common cause of cancer deaths in U.S.
8 women.

9 Now, the incidents of mortality rates for
10 cervical cancer declined dramatically following paps
11 screening and intervention, and for 2001, approximately
12 12,900 new cases of cervical cancer, and approximately
13 4,400 deaths due to cervical cancer have been projected
14 for the U.S.

15 A woman's lifetime risk of developing
16 cervical cancer in the U.S. is currently estimated to
17 be 0.85 percent; and the risk of dying from this disease
18 has been estimated at 0.3 percent.

19 This slide depicts the histological
20 precursor lesions of carcinoma of the cervix, and on the
21 left side you can see the normal epithelium, with orderly
22 maturation.

23 And as you proceed over to the right, you
24 find increasing progression of the abnormalities, and
25 going from CIN-1 to CIN-3, and ultimately over to severe

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1 dysplasia, and then when a full thickness of epithelium
2 is involved, carcinoma in situ.

3 Now, just briefly, I wanted to show you one
4 interesting example where squamos carcinoma in situ,
5 where normal epithelium on the right is just as posed
6 to a full thickness or carcinoma in situ on the left.

7 And of course this case is carcinoma in situ
8 because the basement membrane is intact. This slide
9 depicts the -- if you will, the pyramid of abnormal
10 cervical findings in the U.S., with an ASCUS finding of
11 approximately 2 million cases per year, and then carcinoma
12 of the cervix is much less common, with approximately
13 12,900 cases per year.

14 I am not going to -- we have already covered
15 the natural history, and I am not going to do that, and
16 I did want to make a comment about a study, a worldwide
17 survey of over a thousand invasive cervical cancers, where
18 93 percent were found to be HPV positive by PCR.

19 The five most common types found in the
20 cancers were -- and I listed them on this slide, but the
21 two most common were Types 16 and 18. Subsequently, the
22 negative samples from the study were retested, and 97
23 percent were found to be HPV positive, with more sensitive
24 primers.

25 If one look at the author to find adequate

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1 specimens for this retesting, then the overall rate of
2 positivity was 99.7 percent. I wanted to make a few
3 comments about the differences between squamos cell
4 carcinoma and adenocarcinoma of the cervix.

5 As shown in these two studies, HPV type 16
6 is more common in squamos cell carcinoma of the cervix
7 than is Type HPV 18. Now, this slide shows adenocarcinoma
8 of the cervix, and for adenocarcinoma in a variety of
9 studies, HPV Type 18 is as common or more common than
10 Type 16.

11 And this slide also illustrates another
12 important distinction between squamos cell carcinoma and
13 adenocarcinoma of the cervix. Specifically, cytology
14 screening has had far less impact on the incidents of
15 adenocarcinoma of the cervix, compared to squamos cell
16 carcinoma of the cervix.

17 In the U.S. review of the SEER database has
18 shown a clear decrease in the incidents of squamos cell
19 carcinoma and invasive cervical cancer overall.
20 However, these data have also shown an increase in the
21 rate of adenocarcinoma of the cervix.

22 And interestingly a similar finding has been
23 observed in six Scandinavian countries. I now wanted
24 to cover to longitudinal studies that evaluated the
25 relationship of specific types of HPV to the development

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1 of CIN-2 or 3.

2 In this first study, 241 women presenting
3 for STD evaluation with negative cervical cytology were
4 followed very frequently every 4 months, with an average
5 follow-up of 25 months.

6 And for this follow-up, women had cytology,
7 colposcopy, HPV DNA, as well as testing for STDs. And
8 in this particular study it was found that if the subject
9 was positive for HPV Type 16 or 18, there was an adjusted
10 relative risk of 11 for developing CIN-2 or 3, compared
11 to those without HPV.

12 This is another longitudinal study that was
13 published more recently, and in this study a little over
14 a thousand women with normal cytology and who were HPV
15 negative at baseline were followed every six months with
16 paps smear and HPV DNA.

17 And the median follow-up in this study was
18 26 months. If someone had abnormal cytology, or any
19 abnormality cytology, they were referred to colposcopy
20 and biopsy.

21 Now, in this study there was also found to
22 be an adjusted relative risk of 8.5 for the development
23 of CIN-2 or 3 if one was HPV Type 16 positive at baseline,
24 compared to those who were HPV negative.

25 Now, I want to go on to a specific discussion

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1 of various theoretical endpoints that one might consider
2 for an HPV Types 16 and 18 vaccine. Virology is a
3 potential endpoint, using either any incident infection,
4 or persistent infection, with various definitions, and
5 of course persistent here would also be an incident
6 persistent infection.

7 LSIL cytology or worse with virology is
8 another potential endpoint. CIN-1 histology,
9 adenocarcinoma in situ, or worse with virology, is yet
10 another potential endpoint.

11 And I throw in adenocarcinoma in situ because
12 I think at least theoretically that you have got to
13 consider glandular lesions in your endpoint, although
14 I doubt that many, if any, will be observed in most of
15 the trials that we would see.

16 Another potential endpoint is CIN-2/3
17 histology, adenocarcinoma in situ, or worse with
18 virology; and finally invasive cervical cancer, with or
19 without virology.

20 Now, looking at the virology endpoint, one
21 of the advantages is definitely feasibility, and this
22 could be conducted with a smaller trial, and there are
23 certainly populations in many countries with sufficient
24 incidents of HPV infection.

25 For example, here I give the rate of incident

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1 infections for Type 16. For example, in this one study
2 there was a 10.5 percent cumulative incidence over 3
3 years, and in another study there was a 7 percent
4 cumulative for two years, and so on and so forth.

5 One of the advantages of a virology endpoint
6 is that HPV has been strongly associated with HSIL
7 cytology, carcinoma in situ, and cervical cancer in a
8 variety of studies, some of which are shown here. And
9 certainly you would be able to make an assignment as to
10 whether a case if you will was vaccine versus non-vaccine
11 type.

12 You also might be able to determine an immune
13 correlate of protection if you did the appropriate
14 follow-up post-vaccination serology. However, there are
15 some disadvantages. At least now HPV infection is not
16 a clinical disease.

17 Most HPV infection resolves, and there would
18 be important questions about the durability of
19 protection, especially if one had let's say a trial for
20 several years with virology, and one would wonder about
21 the change in lifetime risk for HSIL, histology, or
22 cancer.

23 Virology is not as approximal to cancer as
24 other endpoints, and it is possible that one may want
25 definitive high grade clinical endpoint data prior to

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1 extensive deployment of a new HPV vaccine.

2 Some other disadvantages are listed on this
3 slide. There is uncertainty in the existence of or
4 detection of latent infections in the cervix, and some
5 of that could be questions about sampling, and you could
6 have HPV theoretically in basal cells, and you might not
7 detect it with a cervical sample.

8 And you may not have it, and there are
9 questions about whether a vaccine might -- a
10 vaccine-induced immune might make HPV DNA more difficult
11 to detect, albeit that is a theoretical.

12 There is also uncertainty in distinguishing
13 new HPV infection from reinfection, although this problem
14 would tend to negatively bias efficacy estimates.

15 And there is also questions about the
16 appropriate definition for persistent infection, and in
17 fact that it has not been clearly validated in prospective
18 longitudinal studies if you will with incident
19 infections, and that a particular definition has not been
20 validated in that sense.

21 It is also possible that the use of virology
22 only may not allow the identification of unanticipated
23 vaccine associated problems. For example, if there was
24 to be enhanced disease for some reason, you might not
25 detect that in a trial designed to look at virology.

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1 Another disadvantage is depending on one's
2 viewpoint is a smaller efficacy trial, because a smaller
3 efficacy trial would provide less well controlled safety
4 data, although that could be addressed with supplemental
5 trials.

6 Now, I wanted to move on to LSIL cytology,
7 or worse. Again, LSIL cytology would have the advantage
8 of feasibility in a smaller trial, and certainly LSIL
9 leads to many clinical workups in developed countries.

10 Disadvantages are shown here. There might
11 be questions about clinical relevance, and LSIL cytology
12 by itself does not represent a definitive diagnosis, and
13 a particular one would need histologic diagnosis usually
14 for therapy.

15 Another disadvantage, and again that it is
16 not as approximal to cancer as other endpoints, and again
17 one may want to have definitive high grade clinical
18 endpoint data before extensive deployment of a new HPV
19 vaccine.

20 And it may be easier to detect or identify
21 unanticipated vaccine associated problems with a high
22 grade disease endpoint, and I have already mentioned the
23 small efficacy trial issue.

24 I am moving on to CIN-1 histology or worse
25 with virology. I would make certain assumptions about

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1 a trial like this, and that is, first, virology would
2 be used to classify the CIN-1 cases as vaccine type or
3 not, just like they would have in the other endpoints.

4 However, one would need to pre-specify
5 whether HPV testing on cervical samples, versus the
6 histology, would be used to classify cases. Cases would
7 be identified mostly from colposcopic workup of atypical
8 squamos cells findings, and LSIL cytology.

9 Obviously, the plan or algorithm for
10 colposcopy will effect the number of endpoints that one
11 attains, and I do want to emphasize that one cannot use
12 economics as the basis for U.S. licensure. It has got
13 to be based on risk benefit.

14 Advantages of CIN-1 histology are worse with
15 virology as an endpoint, and to include feasibility.
16 Certainly there are populations in many countries with
17 sufficient incident of CIN-1.

18 CIN-1 certainly would necessitate a definite
19 workup, and so you would have a definitive diagnosis as
20 your endpoint, and certainly there are data available
21 on the natural history of CIN-1 from an initial diagnosis.

22 Now, CIN-1 histology or worse with virology
23 has certain disadvantages, and at least half of CIN-1
24 resolves without therapy, and also it is not as approximal
25 to cancer as other endpoints.

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1 And one may want definitive high grade
2 clinical endpoint data before extensive deployment of
3 a new HPV vaccine. Again, we have mentioned that it may
4 be easier to identify unanticipated vaccines associated
5 problems with high grade disease endpoints.

6 Now, moving on to CIN-2/3 or worse with
7 virology, I put some assumptions on this slide for such
8 a trial, and again one would need to pre-specify whether
9 it is HPV testing on cervical samples, versus on histology
10 specimens, would be used to classify the cases.

11 Now, many, if not most, CIN-2/3 would be
12 actually identified from colposcopic workup of ASC and
13 LSIL paps smears; and of course the plan or algorithm
14 for colposcopy would be critical to the number of
15 endpoints, and probably even more critical here in a way
16 than in the CIN-1 trial.

17 And I would assume that many, if not most,
18 of the CIN-2/3 cases would be those found at the first
19 workup of abnormal cytology because if there was CIN-1
20 previously, and if it occurred, there might tend to be
21 treatment.

22 Advantages of CIN-2/3 histology or worse with
23 virology is that it is more approximal to cervical cancer,
24 and it would provide a definite high grade clinical
25 endpoint data before widespread public health use.

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1 I think that there is good supporting natural
2 history data, and it prevents lesions that clearly would
3 need therapy by the U.S. standard of care.

4 With this endpoint, it may be easier to
5 identify unanticipated vaccine associated problems, and
6 I think you would be getting into a larger efficacy trial,
7 which would have if you will positive implications for
8 your randomized safety database.

9 The disadvantages of CIN-2/3 as an endpoint
10 are given on this slide, and one of them is feasibility.

11 It may be that the subject numbers may not be that
12 different from most vaccine efficacy trials. As many
13 of you in the audience, we have vaccine efficacy trials
14 that range from 10 to 40,000 and that is not terribly
15 uncommon.

16 However, the thing that is different here
17 is that the type of follow-up per participant is likely
18 to be more resource intensive than perhaps a typical
19 preventive vaccine efficacy trial.

20 There certainly is uncertainty with regard
21 to trial size and duration of the trial. There is really
22 little natural history data to estimate a trial size if
23 one looks for a longitudinal study and very frequent
24 follow-ups, especially in women with a negative baseline
25 HPV normal cytology.

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1 I made a preliminary estimate from a trial
2 that was very recently published by Dr. Woodman, and
3 actually I have already requested some additional
4 information from Dr. Woodman to further refine this.

5 And I believe so as I discovered is one of
6 the sponsors, but I have estimated that for an HPV 16/18
7 vaccine that one would need 12,000 women in a trial, but
8 this would only rule out the lower bound of zero.

9 If you wanted to rule out a lower bound that
10 was higher, you would need to enroll more subjects. And
11 this assumes a vaccine efficacy greater than or equal
12 to 80 percent, which I think is quite conservative if
13 we allowed a sponsor to start counting cases, and let's
14 say after the primary immunization series.

15 It might even be that it would be reasonable
16 to use 85 percent for that estimate. And it would take
17 I would assume 3 years on trial, and at least 6 months
18 for enrollment for a very roughly 3-1/2 year trial.

19 But again I have requested some more
20 information and perhaps we will have a revision of that
21 estimate. Now, I wanted to move on to the example of
22 cervical cancer with or without virology as an endpoint.

23
24 I don't know if anybody would actually
25 propose doing that. There was one publication by a

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1 Scandinavian investigator, Dr. Lightman, who is actually
2 looking at the possibility of cancer. He kind of had
3 a trial that was -- it didn't enroll many people, and
4 it went on for like 15 or 20 years.

5 But I did want to mention though some of the
6 assumptions that one might have if looking at a cervical
7 cancer endpoint in a developed country setting.

8 I assumed that one would randomize subjects,
9 and that there would need to be an infrastructure in place
10 for routine follow-up and a method of capturing all
11 diagnoses for an area.

12 And perhaps a cancer registry and death
13 certificates, and actually in the Scandinavian countries
14 there are comprehensive cancer registries in at least
15 some of the countries that could fulfill that.

16 One critical decision would be HPV testing.

17 I am assuming for all of the previous endpoints that
18 I have mentioned that you would definitely know what your
19 baseline status for HPV was, as well as do HPV testing
20 during the trial.

21 Perhaps given the size of whatever for a
22 cervical cancer trial, that may not be the case, but
23 obviously the presence or absence of baseline testing
24 before randomization, as well as cervical sample
25 histology testing, would affect the efficacy assessment.

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1 And of interest based on at least some data
2 or some studies that I have looked at, I wouldn't be
3 surprised if many or most of the cervical cancer cases
4 were identified from colposcopic work of ASC, AGC, and
5 LSIL.

6 Now, here is some advantages of cervical
7 cancer as an endpoint. Clearly the major concern is
8 cervical cancer. This would be viewed as very, very
9 definitive data, and it may be easier to identify any
10 unanticipated vaccine associated problems.

11 Another advantage of cervical cancer as an
12 endpoint is that I thought it would give a better
13 understanding of the impact of the vaccine on
14 adenocarcinoma, which has been increasing as I mentioned
15 in incidents.

16 And again you would have a larger efficacy
17 trial, which would be good, although I suspect that with
18 this sort of trial that you might not have detailed
19 information on the participants.

20 The major disadvantage of cervical cancer
21 in an endpoint is feasibility, and uncertainty with regard
22 to trial size, duration, population selection, and there
23 may be issues in looking at countries without screening
24 program, and so on and so forth.

25 I did want to make a couple of other comments

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1 about endpoints for HPV vaccines. Obviously the protocol
2 would need to specify the handling of mixed infections,
3 especially vaccine versus non-vaccine types
4 prospectively in the primary endpoint, and I believe that
5 there would need to be evidence of overall benefit from
6 all endpoints, including ones attributed to non-vaccine
7 high risk HPV types, and are included in the analysis.

8 In other words, we may well -- and I suspect
9 that we would allow a sponsor to use vaccine types of
10 HPV for their primary analysis, and that would mean the
11 non-vaccine types would not be included in the primary
12 analysis.

13 However, again we would also like to see the
14 impact on the disease as a whole. I wanted to briefly
15 go over accelerated approvals since it has been raised
16 several times today.

17 The accelerated approval regulations kind
18 of apply to new biological products, and also to drugs,
19 and they are intended for biological products for serious
20 or life-threatening illnesses. And these should be
21 products that provide meaningful therapeutic benefit to
22 patients over existing treatments.

23 The FDA may grant marketing approval for a
24 biological product on the basis of adequate and well
25 controlled clinical trials establishing that a biological

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1 product has an effect on a surrogate endpoint that is
2 reasonably likely based on epidemiologic, therapeutic,
3 pathophysiologic, or other evidence to predict clinical
4 benefit from the basis of an effect on a clinical endpoint
5 other than survival or irreversible morbidity.

6 That is a real mouthful I know, and it may
7 take a minute or two to digest it, but that is the guidance
8 from the regulation. And the purpose of the accelerated
9 approval regulations is that they are intended to make
10 available promising therapies while definitive,
11 confirmatory efficacy trials or trial is being completed.

12 And the confirmatory post-marketing study
13 is usually well underway at the time of accelerated
14 approval. It is like the trial of the surrogate, the
15 trial for the confirmatory endpoint must be adequate and
16 well controlled, and it must be carried out with due
17 diligence.

18 The original and current purpose of
19 accelerated approval is to serve the best interests of
20 the public, and I did want to note that presented vaccines
21 have not been previously approved using accelerated
22 approval regulations.

23 So I did want to bring that to your attention.

24 Most of the products that have been approved using
25 accelerated approval regulations has been AIDS therapies

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1 and cancer therapies.

2 Now, in concluding, I would like to re-review
3 the FDA questions for you to think about before our
4 discussion in more detail tomorrow; and that is -- and
5 again I have got two questions.

6 One is please discuss and identify the most
7 appropriate endpoints for traditional approval of HPV
8 vaccines intended to prevent cervical cancer. And in
9 particular please discuss the use of the following
10 endpoints in clinical trials intended to demonstrate the
11 efficacy of HPV vaccines for oncogenic types in the
12 indications, such as prevention of HPV infection that
13 these endpoints would support.

14 And listed here are incident HPV infection
15 by oncogenic HPV types; persistent HPV infection by
16 oncogenic HPV types; and regarding the persistent
17 infection endpoint, we would also ask that you discuss
18 the appropriate number of positive virologic results in
19 the interval between such positive virologic results.

20 Again, another candidate endpoint is LSIL
21 cytology, associated with oncogenic HPV types; CIN-1
22 associated with oncogenic HPV types; and CIN-2/3
23 associated with oncogenic HPV types; and finally cervical
24 cancer.

25 For the second question, please discuss the

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1 use of accelerated approval regulations for licensure
2 of HPV vaccines for the prevention of cervical cancer.

3 Specifically, please discuss and identify possible
4 surrogate endpoints to support accelerated approval.

5 In particular, please consider the following
6 endpoints. Incident HPV infection by oncogenic HPV
7 types; persistent HPV infection by oncogenic HPV types;
8 LSIL cytology associated with oncogenic HPV types; and
9 CIN-1 histology associated with oncogenic HPV types.

10 And also in the context of accelerated
11 approval, please discuss and identify possible endpoints
12 for the confirmatory trial. Thank you very much.

13 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much, Karen.

14 I would like to see if there is some comment or discussion
15 from committee members specifically regarding
16 clarification of what Dr. Goldenthal has said. We will
17 start with Dr. Snider.

18 DR. SNIDER: I just would like to have some
19 clarification in the context based on conversations that
20 we have had today, and I will try to be appropriately
21 discreet about what information was presented in closed
22 session or open session.

23 But my understanding is that we are being
24 asked this question in the context of the deliberation
25 by professional societies and guidelines making

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1 organizations which are considering the data available
2 today.

3 It may or it appeared to be sometime in the
4 near future coming out with some recommendations, and
5 which may include recommendations for intervention in
6 the context of persistent infection, and we don't at this
7 time know exactly what those recommendations would be.

8 But that is the context in which we operate.

9 We also are being asked to respond to these questions
10 in the context of a large prospective study being
11 analyzed, data from a large study be analyzed, which would
12 be informative about optimal intervals to define
13 persistent infections, and perhaps identify risk factors
14 that indicate persistent infections might progress to
15 cancer or to high grade lesions, CIN-2/3.

16 So we are being asked these questions in the
17 context of there soon being some information that will
18 impinge on our answers, but we don't yet have that
19 information. Is that correct?

20 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Yes. Well, I mean, you are
21 absolutely right. It is difficult --

22 DR. SNIDER: Well, it is a moving target,
23 but these are some very significant limitations I think
24 that are going to be difficult for us to deal with, and
25 let me just express my frustration in that regard.

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1 DR. GOLDENTHAL: And the different
2 therapeutic approaches may differ from country to
3 country, which could be complex for a multi-country trial.

4 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Dr. Fleming, and then Dr.
5 Kohl.

6 DR. FLEMING: Dr. Goldenthal, a couple of
7 questions. First, I am assuming as you have laid out
8 these two questions for us, one on endpoints, that might
9 be appropriate surrogate endpoints to use for traditional
10 or full approval and those for accelerated approval, I
11 am assuming that we have flexibility in proposing
12 alternatives, or combinations of these, or variations
13 of these?

14 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Absolutely. These
15 questions, they are both in a please discuss mode, and
16 I think you do have flexibility.

17 DR. FLEMING: Okay. Moving along in that
18 direction, a couple of more questions. This is -- and
19 following kind of Dixie's spirit, this is a very
20 significant challenge, partly because it is always
21 complex to talk about what are valid surrogates, and
22 generally the type of information you need to even begin
23 to truly address this with insight is not only natural
24 history of it, but it is what are the relationships between
25 various markers and clinical outcomes, and natural

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1 history.

2 But also what are those relationships, in
3 the context of people who are receiving intervention of
4 interest, and essentially we lack that type of insight.

5 We are also lacking as Dixie was pointing
6 out some of the insight even in natural history. When
7 I look at your list, you have listed as a major
8 disadvantage for CIN-2/3 in particular logistical
9 practicality, and that it is going to be a study that
10 is going to be too large, and it is somewhat difficult
11 to really assess that.

12 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, I was more thinking
13 in terms of resource intensiveness per participant,
14 compared to other preventive vaccines. The final size
15 -- you know, again we have trials in the 10 to 40,000
16 range, but this is a lot of follow-up on individuals in
17 the trial, compared to many other trials.

18 DR. FLEMING: I understand. There are some
19 very helpful sources of information in the literature.

20 The Woodman article, for example, that you referred to,
21 does give us a sense if you follow a cohort of uninfected
22 individuals from time zero ahead, that we have something
23 on the order of an accumulative risk of CIN-2/3 that might
24 approach one percent by about 4 years follow-up.

25 You have also given some specific indications

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1 of lifetime risks, where for a thousand people lifetime
2 risk of death due to cervical cancer might be three in
3 a thousand, and maybe nine in a thousand would have a
4 diagnosis of cervical cancer.

5 And you have also told us that the actual
6 annual incidences of CIN-2/3 might be 20-fold annually
7 higher than diagnosis of cancer. So clearly one is left
8 with a sense that over time there is a very high cumulative
9 risk of CIN-2/3.

10 One of the things that I am struggling with
11 though is to get a sense of if that risk based on the
12 Woodman data over 3 years to 4 years might approach 7/10s
13 of a percent to one percent, is there a sense as to whether
14 that risk is essentially linear?

15 Will that increase at that rate? Let's say
16 you are looking at a cohort of 16 to 23 year old women
17 at randomization, and if their risk is .25 percent a year
18 for the first several years, is that likely to, if
19 anything, go up a bit as those women approach their mid-20s
20 and late-20s? Does anybody have a sense about that?

21 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Who would like to take on
22 that question?

23 DR. GOLDENTHAL: It is interesting, because
24 I would have predicted that it would -- that the increase
25 would not be linear. That it would go up a lot. In other

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1 words, in year four of a trial might be more than year
2 two of a trial.

3 And I think you will get some of that in a
4 trial, but I have been a little bit surprised, at least
5 in two of the longitudinal studies, how quickly HPV --
6 how quickly CIN-2/3 developed following HPV infection.

7 I think, for example, in the Woodman study
8 that they mentioned that the median time from the first
9 detection of HPV to diagnosis of CIN-2/3 was 26 months.

10 So I do think that your -- let's say your second, third
11 and fourth year will probably be enriched compared to
12 your first year, in terms of diagnoses.

13 But I don't know -- you know, assuming that
14 the HPV infection rate or whatever stays high -- and it
15 certainly did seem to stay high in some of these cohorts.

16 But that is a difficult question to answer. I think
17 that there would be definitely value added from going
18 from four years to three years, for example, in such a
19 trial. Perhaps some of the sponsors can or others can
20 address this better.

21 CHAIRMAN DAUM: If people have information
22 about this very issue, we will entertain that. Dr. Felix,
23 do you?

24 DR. FELIX: Well, there is natural
25 occurrence of CIN-2/3 that is in an older age group.

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1 So, every subsequent year one would predict the frequency
2 of that diagnosis to increase not -- and most of the
3 studies that that has been shown in are not HPV -- do
4 not examine virologic status.

5 The Woodman study perhaps, as well as the
6 Koutsky study, showing the very brief interval, is because
7 of the prevalent HPV in those two studies. I mean, a
8 significant or a very large majority, and in Koutsky,
9 all of them already had HPV positivity at entry.

10 And again your point taken, you don't know
11 how long that has been and what time zero was in those
12 women, and we don't have a naive cohort analyzed so far.

13 So I think there is very good existing natural history
14 data that would predict an increase in incidents as the
15 population matures in age.

16 MR. JONES: My name is Bruce James, and I
17 have a personal communication from Eduardo Franco, who
18 is one of the co-principal investigators for a cohort
19 study, a natural history study, in Sao Paulo, Brazil,
20 in which women 18 to 60, were enrolled over a 3 year period,
21 and then followed initially in the first year of
22 observation three times, and then annually thereafter.

23 And we asked him to -- well, the median age
24 of this group was 33, with about one-quarter of the
25 enrollees under the age of 25. And we asked Eduardo

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1 recently to look at his data and tell us in women who
2 were initially HPV negative, and had no SIL, what the
3 pattern of HSIL was.

4 And what he saw was if you looked in all age
5 groups, the accumulation of lesions really stopped after
6 about 3 years; and if you looked at women who were under
7 25, it stopped after 2 years of observations.

8 So there are small numbers involved and this
9 is a group of about 1,100 women that were followed, but
10 it would suggest that there is not clearly a linear
11 increase.

12 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very kindly. Dr.
13 Schiffman.

14 DR. SCHIFFMAN: In Costa Rica, in our
15 Portland cohorts, we see a much greater than expected
16 percentage of what we initially thought was incident high
17 grade, and it turned out to be missed-prevalent high
18 grade.

19 I caution you when you are looking at any
20 study of the old cohorts or whatever to think carefully
21 about how did they rule out small high grade lesions,
22 and what did they use, and how many techniques did they
23 use.

24 And as you were saying before, how many were
25 colposcopic, and was there any kind of an attempt to look

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1 at or for false negatives, because the more that you look
2 -- we have dropped progression rates from 17 percent to
3 6 percent by more careful review of initially what was
4 thought to be totally negative initial entry criteria.

5 In Costa Rica, in Portland, what we see is
6 this burst in HPV infected women who are normal,
7 cytologically and totally normal, and we see this burst
8 of apparent incident detection that we think is
9 false-negative detection. In other words, it was already
10 there.

11 And then a trough, which appears to be some
12 kind of latency that is fairly short, and then we see
13 a pickup where CIN-2 is fairly steady, and it is ticking
14 along as people get HPV, and then pretty rapidly get CIN-2,
15 even young women who are virginal and then get their
16 incident infection.

17 CIN-3 with some delay, picking up a little
18 bit later, and the predictive value of HPV DNA test in
19 those women by 7 years or so has dropped off entirely.

20 So it is a complex phenomenon, and I do not think
21 particularly that the Woodman article captured all those
22 subtleties.

23 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much.

24 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Although they certainly did
25 have a frequent follow-up. That has been the best that

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1 I have been able to find in terms of a longitudinal cohort.

2 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much. Dr.
3 Kohl, you have been patient.

4 DR. KOHL: I have been patient. My head
5 right now is in the Dixie mindset of contextual issues,
6 and a couple of things come to mind. If we advise studies
7 that involve higher grade findings, CIN-2/3, for
8 instance, then those studies essentially will have to
9 have also virological data associated with that I would
10 think, because it would be CIN-2/3 with high grade virus.

11 And then the context is that we obviously
12 have lots of other evolving information coming;
13 guidelines and natural history studies. And my question
14 is do we need to make some advice for all time, or can
15 it be a temporary advice, in which case there might be
16 a more rigorous criteria, which as more information
17 evolve, we could then fall back to a virological surrogate
18 if that proves to be feasible and useful as we get more
19 long term natural history done.

20 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, as you know -- I mean,
21 we take advice from committees, but then things can
22 potentially evolve, and what is used to prove -- well,
23 a good example of that over a longer period of time is
24 what may be used for one approval may not be used -- you
25 know, may not be for the next approval, in terms of

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1 endpoints, and so on, and so forth.

2 So we certainly do consider evolution, and
3 it is possible that we may bring this question back to
4 the VRBPAC at some point in the not too distant future.

5 But I think for the purposes of the meeting today, I
6 think you have to advise us on the available information.

7 I mean, I could argue that we maybe should
8 have had this meeting six months ago, but that is the
9 problem with this area. Every time I wanted to have a
10 meeting, I thought, oh, good, some new data came out,
11 and it sort of narrowed things down.

12 And I understand this point a little better,
13 but then there are these other three points that we don't
14 know about. I mean, I think you have got to give us advice
15 for now, and if you want to make comments on advice for
16 the future, you are welcome to do that, too.

17 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Karen, I would like to ask
18 a question actually about the implications of accelerated
19 approval for patients in the actual use of the vaccine.

20
21 And I am wondering if you could accept an
22 assumption that, for example, some early endpoint is
23 chosen for the initial trial, or the initial checkpoint.

24 I may not be using quite the right terminology here.

25 But let's say a vaccine is shown to prevent

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1 HPV infection, and let's say that on the accelerated
2 approval track that a confirmatory trial is set up, and
3 the agency begins processing data and preparing for
4 licensure, and allowing use based on the HPV infection
5 prevention dataset.

6 The trial is then going on to say, prevent
7 CIN-2/3, and just to make something up for the sake of
8 the question. And so at what point would the accelerated
9 approval actually allow use of the vaccine publicly, and
10 would the trial, the CIN-2/3 prevention trial, still be
11 going on?

12 And there are two obvious questions there.

13 Would placebo people still be enrollable at that point;
14 and then secondly -- well, would the vaccine be out there
15 in use and people actually able to use it earlier with
16 this accelerated approval?

17 And would people still be able to be able
18 to be enrolled into the placebo arm of a confirmatory
19 trial?

20 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, here is my thought
21 on the issue. I think that potentially -- and we have
22 not done this before in the agency, at least for preventive
23 vaccine. But my thought in this setting is that
24 accelerated approval might buy you a year in terms of
25 coming out on the market earlier.

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1 I mean, this is what I would envision. A
2 sponsor would have a CIN, and let's say for example a
3 CIN-2/3 efficacy trial ongoing. And then for that
4 particular -- and that study would be very well enrolled
5 in my opinion even at the time a BLA would be submitted
6 with the virology endpoint.

7 And then that BLA would be under review by
8 the agency and it would go through its review cycle, and
9 so on and so forth. And at some point -- and let's just
10 take an example. Let's say that all issues were resolved
11 a year after approval, or a year after BLA submission.

12 I would think that that confirmatory, at
13 least in the U.S., I would think that that confirmatory
14 CIN-2/3 trial would basically have to be finished at about
15 the time of approval, because I think it would be untenable
16 to have that trial ongoing.

17 So again by my math, in the U.S. it would
18 buy you about a year, and some may argue that that year
19 might be valuable. It might even buy you more than a
20 year, because again you would have that CIN-2/3 -- well,
21 because at the point that you get the result of that
22 CIN-2/3 trial, the sponsor has got to QC the data, and
23 they have got to QC the trial, and they have got to write
24 it up, and they have got to submit it to the agency.

25 And we have then got to review it, and then

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1 that is going to be a boat load of data, and so again
2 that is how I am kind of coming up with a year. That
3 is very rough.

4 DR. SNIDER: Karen, could I just sort of
5 press you a little bit more on the accelerated approval
6 issue.

7 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Sure.

8 DR. SNIDER: Because I understand what you
9 are saying, and the way that it has been described to
10 us before in the accelerated approval is that there is
11 one study, and then there is the confirmatory study.

12 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, in some cases it is
13 even the same study.

14 DR. SNIDER: Okay. That was my next
15 question. Could you design one study that would allow
16 you then to be looking at more than one endpoint, and
17 then as things evolve make hopefully appropriate
18 decisions about whether to continue on, or --

19 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, theoretically, yes.
20 CDER has definitely done that with AIDS drugs, and so
21 on and so forth. Obviously you are blinding and all that
22 would have to be just so. I would not again have an issue
23 with that trial continuing prior to approval.

24 The issue would be whether -- well, we would
25 need a high level of assurance that things are going to

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1 get done.

2 CHAIRMAN DAUM: I think we are going to go
3 to Ms. Fisher, Dr. Fleming, and Dr. Kohl, and then we
4 are going to conclude Dr. Goldenthal's presentation.
5 We will have an opportunity to revisit these issues in
6 as much depth as you like, but we are looking to clarify
7 what Dr. Goldenthal is telling us how about the questions
8 and FDA procedures, and what they would like to hear about.
9 Ms. Fisher.

10 MS. FISHER: If this is the first vaccine
11 that is going to potentially be subject to the accelerated
12 approval process, how does the accelerated approval
13 process impact on the gathering of safety data prior to
14 licensure?

15 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, I would -- you know,
16 that is a very good question, and we would have to at
17 FDA consider what is the minimum amount of safety data,
18 and I would prefer that it be randomized prior to approval.

19 So that is a very good question.

20 MS. FISHER: Well, if we were to give the
21 indication to the FDA that we wanted an accelerated
22 approval process here, we have not had any discussion
23 in any depth about safety. In other words is there going
24 to be another meeting that is going to talk about safety
25 data?

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1 DR. GOLDENTHAL: Well, we did not have a
2 specific advisory committee meeting planned, but since
3 that would be a factor in -- again, this meeting is focused
4 on the endpoint question because that seemed to be the
5 most -- you know, where the most, if you will, controversy
6 had been coming up.

7 But if you have views about the amount of
8 safety data for this particular product needed prior to
9 traditional approval, or accelerated approval, please
10 feel free to speak up. But I do want to make sure that
11 we do cover the endpoint issue in this meeting.

12 CHAIRMAN DAUM: We will. Dr. Fleming,
13 please.

14 DR. FLEMING: Actually, I wanted to continue
15 on the line of questioning that I had done earlier, and
16 actually in a sense follow up with a thought similar to
17 Dixie's thought.

18 The question that I had asked earlier I know
19 was a difficult question, and that is if you randomize
20 -- and let's say hypothetically 10,000 women who are about
21 age 20, who are HPV negative, and you follow ahead, and
22 you design a trial, and targeting CIN-2/3, and you are
23 looking at needing to detect a reduction in this rate
24 at let's say 3 to 4 years follow-up.

25 It is my sense that if you followed those

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1 people beyond three years for an additional two years,
2 that the number of cases of CIN-2/3 should increase
3 linearly. You are starting at time zero with pristine
4 negative cohort, and during that first three years those
5 people will begin to have HPV infection.

6 And some of them will be rapid progressors,
7 and some of them more slow progressors. But logic would
8 tell me that if you take a cross-sectional snapshot of
9 those people at 3 years, you are going to have a cohort
10 more advanced than the pristine time zero cohort at
11 randomization.

12 And the additional 2 years from -- and let's
13 say from your 3 to your 5, could readily yield much more
14 than the number of CIN-2/3 cases that you saw in the first
15 3 years. Why is that relevant?

16 Well, it is related to the point that Dixie
17 was stating, which is in essence might the same trial
18 in essence -- and even at the same endpoint, be an
19 accelerated approval endpoint, versus a full approval
20 endpoint?

21 Specifically, if you were looking at the zero
22 -- and as Dr. Goldenthal had pointed out, if you were
23 designing a trial to simply rule out no reduction, when
24 in truth you expect an 80 percent reduction, it takes
25 a relatively small number of actual cases, on the order

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1 of 20 to 23.

2 Well, there are some disadvantages to this,
3 even if we said CIN-2/3 is in essence an acceptable
4 surrogate endpoint, if you are only looking at the very
5 earliest emergence of CIN-2/3, and you show a reduction
6 in that earliest emergence, that is in essence also just
7 a surrogate for the more global protective effect against
8 CIN-2/3.

9 And so one approach might well be to design
10 a trial that is targeting CIN-2/3 over a longer time frame,
11 such as 5 to 6 years, where at 3 years, when you have
12 enough evidence to rule out a quality on the CIN-2/3
13 endpoint, you have accelerated approval, possibly backed
14 up with persistent infection evidence as well at that
15 point, which would be adequately powered because that
16 would take a smaller sample size.

17 And the backing up by persistent infection
18 would be giving you a bit of a more global perspective
19 of what you might be anticipating in future years on
20 CIN-2/3.

21 Then you have a cohort that is well under
22 way, and so even if accelerated approval kicks in with
23 access to cross-in's, it will have a less deluding effect
24 on what your ultimate assessment might be 2 or 3 years
25 later, where you might have 2 to 3-fold the number of

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1 cases.

2 And if you do, now if you have 50 cases to
3 60, now you can look at a test of .5 versus .8, and
4 specifically if you have 80 percent vaccine efficacy now
5 at 5 years, you can rule out that you have less than 50
6 percent, which is a very relevant issue.

7 Often with vaccines we expect this. We
8 expect to be able to say not only is there 80 percent
9 protection, but actually I am convinced that there is
10 at least 50 percent protection. So there is a very
11 tangible significant payoff in exchange for what will
12 be a very broad exposure program.

13 So just to plant the seed, one approach that
14 could be taken here would in essence be to do one trial
15 that would still only have to be of the size of 10 to
16 15 thousand people, but you get the additional data by
17 additional follow-up, which is consistent with the
18 concept of accelerated approval.

19 You are getting the answer in the earlier
20 time for an accelerated approval, and you are then
21 continuing for additional time to get a more global
22 reliable sense of what the effect is.

23 CHAIRMAN DAUM: All right. That is a very
24 helpful comment. Thank you very much, Dr. Fleming. I
25 think at this point that we will thank Dr. Goldenthal

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1 very much for her presentation, and turn to the open public
2 hearing portion of our meeting.

3 We have three speakers scheduled to address
4 the committee, the first of which is Ms. Cindy Pearson,
5 from the National Women's Health Network, and her comments
6 are related to the considerations that we have had today.

7 Ms. Pearson. She has been asked and been budgeted for
8 10 minutes to present to us.

9 MS. PEARSON: I am Cindy Pearson, and I am
10 the executive director of the National Women's Health
11 Network. Our disclosure statement is that we are an
12 independent, non-profit consumer advocacy group,
13 supported by small progressive foundations, and a
14 national membership of approximately 9,000 women, who
15 live in all 50 States.

16 We do not accept any financial support from
17 drug companies, or device manufacturers. We are frequent
18 visitors to FDA advisory committee meetings, although
19 not to this one. We are more commonly active in
20 reflective health drugs and OB-GYN devices, and metabolic
21 and endocrine drugs.

22 It is interesting to come here and testify
23 today because in my actual 13 years of visiting FDA
24 advisory committee meetings, I think this is the only
25 one that has not had its sponsor presentation open to

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1 the public.

2 And I will just share that comment with you.

3 That is an interesting choice, and I understand what
4 guidelines the FDA has that allow it to have closed
5 meetings and when they are useful and even necessary.
6 But just to give you that feedback.

7 From the perspective of a woman's health
8 group that brings the voice of average women to places
9 where decisions are made in Washington, D.C., we are
10 delighted to see sponsors coming to the FDA and supporting
11 the interests and efforts that have been made by the public
12 health community in the quest for a preventive vaccine
13 for HPV disease.

14 I don't want to repeat anything that you have
15 heard 17 times already today about how important this
16 disease is worldwide, and how important it is in the United
17 States.

18 I will just make a point that I haven't heard
19 made this afternoon, which is that it is particularly
20 important I think to low income women and women of color
21 in the United States. African-American women are less
22 likely to be screened routinely, and have the opportunity
23 to find changes early when they can be treated more
24 effectively than less basically.

25 And particularly new Asian immigrant women,

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1 Vietnamese-American women, have the highest rate of
2 cervical cancer in the United States, and much more
3 reflecting the rate of cervical cancer in the country
4 from which they have come, and other new Asian immigrants.

5 So even though overall we look at cases of
6 cancer and likelihood of death from cervical cancer that
7 are very small in, and you might say low on the priority
8 list for women in the U.S.

9 But as a broad-based consumer group, we are
10 aware that for certain groups of women in the United States
11 that it is much higher on the priority list.

12 So I want to be specific in our comments about the endpoint
13 question, because that is what you are struggling with
14 here today.

15 And I think we have a perspective that might
16 be useful to you in the average woman's views. I would
17 say to put it very, very -- and oversimplified to the
18 average woman, whether this prevents HPV infection isn't
19 really all that important, because the average woman is
20 probably infected with HPV, and has it resolved, and never
21 knows.

22 A very common experience though -- and I
23 acknowledge -- is that a woman is told that she has an
24 HPV inspection, and she has what she is told a very bad
25 pap, and there is some follow-up, and she gets her HPV

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1 infection results, and then has some worry about the
2 commonly known association with cervical cancer.

3 But I would still put forth the perspective
4 from our consumer group that a vaccine that is either
5 approved preliminarily through accelerated approval, or
6 finally through final approval based on its ability to
7 prevent either infinite infection or persistent
8 infection, isn't really making that much of a difference
9 in women's lives.

10 And obviously ideally the real difference
11 would be to prevent those cases of cervical cancers that
12 have the possibility of killing women. But we are as
13 aware as you of the long, long time that it would take
14 for the need to do it in a country where resources are
15 so low that that is almost all that you can measure.

16 Probably the best -- from our perspective
17 the best way to go in what would be potentially a
18 multi-country trial, possibly involving the United
19 States, is the point at which -- having the endpoint of
20 the vaccine prevention trial be the point at which most
21 women would face treatment if this vaccine never came
22 into use in the country in which it is being tested.

23 We all heard that most women automatically
24 face the definitive treatment if they are diagnosed with
25 CIN-2/3 or HSIL, and in well-insured women in the United

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1 States, many women are getting a lot more treatment that
2 has been pointed out a couple of times, in follow-up
3 studies and treatments that they probably don't need.

4 And I recognize that a well-intentioned
5 person could make a strong argument for having an endpoint
6 being earlier at the LSIL point, or the CIN-1 point.
7 I think we would probably not want to sort of cave in
8 to the fact that there is a lot of over-treatment and
9 over-use of repeat testing in the United States, and push
10 the endpoint back earlier just because that is the reality
11 in the United States. But it is not the appropriate
12 reality, even though it is the reality.

13 And I also wanted to comment on something
14 that I thought I heard inside, is that there may be a
15 context in which the FDA has asked you all to come and
16 work hard, and think hard, and give advice, which might
17 lead to you recommending an endpoint which 2 or 3 years
18 from now doesn't exist anymore in the United States
19 because of looming guidelines that may be issued by
20 primary care groups, who you may think may be posed to
21 recommend treatment long before any of these endpoints
22 come into play.

23 I would argue from the consumers' perspective
24 that it is the FDA and its own deliberative process that
25 gets to the true public health benefit of treatment,

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1 drugs, devices, and preventive vaccines, more than the
2 specialty societies with their day to day contact with
3 people who are already being treated or are suffering
4 from late-stage disease.

5 That this is the one place we have as a society
6 to bring in the balances and checks that help us have
7 a conversation about what the product in the end can really
8 make the most difference in women's lives.

9 So those are the thoughts that we wanted to
10 share with you, and we appreciate the opportunity to do
11 so; and if anyone wants to ask me a question, you're
12 welcome.

13 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much, Ms.
14 Pearson.

15 MS. PEARSON: You're welcome.

16 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Our next presenter is --

17 DR. HILDESHEIM: I have one or two comments.

18 CHAIRMAN DAUM: We will permit one or two
19 comments. We don't usually do that in open public
20 hearings.

21 DR. HILDESHEIM: I just wanted to state that
22 I am with the National Cancer Institute and we are
23 sponsoring one of the trials, which is publicly financed,
24 and we share your desire for open sessions.

25 And our trial is open and you are welcome

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1 to have any information that you would like of the protocol
2 and details you might want.

3 MS. PEARSON: Thanks.

4 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much, Ms.
5 Pearson. Our next speaker is Ms. Karen Forschner, a
6 representative or member at least of the Lyme Disease
7 Foundation, who has some comments on LYMERix vaccine,
8 and has asked and been budgeted for between 6 and 10
9 minutes. Ms. Forschner, welcome.

10 MS. FORSCHNER: Thank you for having me
11 today. I think most of the committee members have a copy
12 of the statement. What you will be receiving is each
13 of the exhibits sometime in the next week from Nancy
14 Cherry, I believe.

15 And she will be making copies for you that
16 go along with this. I am Karen Vanderhoof-Forschner,
17 a mother whose child was born with, handicapped by, and
18 died from Lyme disease.

19 In 1988, before he died, I co-founded the
20 Lyme Disease Foundation with a team of distinguished
21 leaders who trailblazed into the world unaware of Lyme
22 disease, and within two years, made Lyme disease a
23 household term.

24 The LDF has always fostered vaccine
25 development, and we have always appreciated the value

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1 of vaccines in preventing terrible illnesses. My son
2 had received all his childhood vaccines. My daughter
3 is current in all of her vaccines.

4 My aunt, who suffered from polio, could have
5 had a much richer life if there was a vaccine that she
6 had taken. I take the flu vaccine every year, and our
7 pets have always been fully vaccinated.

8 And many of you may remember me from the 1998
9 vaccine meeting, where LYMERix was approved for us. I
10 am back. Based on the new data that we have seen in the
11 last 6 months, and the data that you will be receiving
12 later, I believe that the OspA-Vaccine represents an
13 imminent and substantial hazard to the public health,
14 and needs to be immediately recalled.

15 I believe that the vaccine process has been
16 seriously flawed. Information has been withheld from
17 the vaccine advisory committee, and possibly the FDA,
18 and that experts that could have helped provide
19 information were never invited to participate, enough
20 to compromise all of the trial data, and even to cast
21 doubts on the integrity of the investigators.

22 Please take this as a clear warning to you,
23 the FDA, and the vaccine advisory committee, that we are
24 asking you to demand that the manufacturers fully complete
25 all safety and efficacy studies and never again let them

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1 promise you a study tomorrow for your approval today.

2 The FDA's decisive action is important to
3 pull this from the product. Let me cover several sections
4 that I believe are important. As you know, there has
5 been great concern about the OspA vaccine having a
6 cross-reactive effect to certain genetically vulnerable
7 populations.

8 In May of '95, even the principal
9 investigator in the vaccine stated that he felt a small
10 number of people in the vaccine were having vaccine
11 related adverse reactions.

12 In '98, he published finding the actual
13 potential autoantigen to the OspA-vaccine. There was
14 a meeting in January of this year, an excellent meeting,
15 to take a look at the safety.

16 Unfortunately, and in cases of adverse events
17 related to the vaccine were published and presented at
18 scientific meetings. What you didn't know was that in
19 the fall of '99, scientists that were involved in trials
20 found that they modify the polypeptides in the
21 OspA-vaccine and knew exactly which ones to modify to
22 reduce side effects that could be attributed to the
23 vaccine, and then patented this.

24 The patent was on the web and you can see
25 the genetic codes that they modified, and you can see

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1 the test that they performed, comparing regular
2 OspA-vaccine to their new modified, safer vaccine.

3 And indeed in the patent it says there exists
4 an urgent need for an improved vaccine for the prevention
5 of Lyme disease, and they were able to show that the
6 OspA-vaccine causes increased self-binding, increased
7 human T-cell proliferation response, increased cytokine
8 production compared their safer vaccine.

9 I believe at this point the theory is ended
10 and we now know that there is a threat. There are also
11 violation entries or violations of entry criteria.

12 Instead of healthy people as an entry, and
13 then the exclusion of those having associated joint
14 swelling and musculoskeletal problems, which indeed they
15 enroll people in the study within six weeks, about 20
16 percent of those people are in violation to the entry
17 criteria.

18 This includes people with osteoarthritis,
19 clinical depression, multiple sclerosis, Parkinson's
20 Disease, abnormal movement disorders, and the list goes
21 on.

22 The concern we have is that by a 20 percent
23 violation, which has as far as we know not been reported
24 to IRB, or to the patients themselves, you put a vulnerable
25 population at risk.

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1 I also included in this a sample of some of
2 the people, their prior history, and what was attributed
3 to the vaccine or not. Anyone that had a prior history
4 of any musculoskeletal problems that then had a problem
5 during the vaccine process, it was declared not related.

6
7 The only one that I could find in an FOI was
8 a woman who had menopause, and at that point her adverse
9 reaction was attributed to possibly the vaccine. There
10 are serious concerns from the FDA data on the protocol
11 itself, and on how the data was reported.

12 According to SmithKline, there are two people
13 with neurologic Lyme disease that came out of this study.

14 Unfortunately, they had serious flaws, and they had the
15 right to choose, to decline to do spinal taps, and EMGs
16 on patients, and without that, the patients that had
17 neurologic Lyme could not be categorized as definite Lyme.

18 So of those two that were reported as having
19 Bell's palsy, there happened to be an additional 414 that
20 were all of a sudden reported that still don't show up
21 on the slide shows and presentations that are given.

22 The problem that SmithKline said was that
23 they found that they had not included a code for facial
24 nerve disorder, and therefore, they weren't reportable.

25 And for those that did have Bell's palsy, they decided

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1 to report them only if they had an EM rash at the same
2 time.

3 Through the FOI, we found repeated problems,
4 including the fact that there was a patient diagnosed
5 with meningoencephalitis that did not receive a spinal
6 tap, and received oral medication which is outside the
7 standard of care for this protocol.

8 There was a patient that was in the hospital
9 with diagnosed Lyme meningitis, and a spinal tap was
10 performed and not tested. Those people were not
11 afforded. Indeed, there was an analysis of those with
12 the Western positive versus Western block negative that
13 showed those who were Western block positive had an
14 increased incident of late adverse events, including skin
15 and appendage disorder, musculoskeletal system disorder,
16 central and peripheral nervous system disorders,
17 autonomic nervous system disorders, psychiatric
18 disorders, gastrointestinal disorders, white cell and
19 RES disorders, and resistant disorders.

20 This information did not make the package insert.

21 There are people that I am suggesting for
22 any other vaccine advisory committee when the next
23 generation of Lyme vaccine comes along, and I am concerned
24 that the vaccine committee who I have called members that
25 were on as expert witness in January were unaware of any

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1 of this data that I presented to you so far.

2 They were also unaware that the pediatric
3 data was available, and that the Connaught vaccine data
4 was available. They were unaware that we had been told,
5 the Lyme Disease Foundation, that there was a Harvard
6 study -- not the Harvard Pilgrim study, a study that was
7 done earlier that showed some of these adverse events,
8 and whether or not they were related, and it has not been
9 published, and it has not been presented.

10 In July, after this meeting, we found a press
11 clipping where GlaxoSmithKline indicated that they were
12 about ready to start another Phase III trial with 10 to
13 15,000 people. New York had legislation introduced to
14 mandate this vaccine for all the pediatric population
15 in the State.

16 OSHA was working on a mandate, and there was
17 a mandate in the Federal Government for legislation for
18 Medicare to cover the vaccine. Even the fundamental rule
19 of a vaccine and how it works is not even correct.

20 As you know the vaccine works by your
21 immunized blood going into the tick. If you read the
22 study which I have presented in the packet, it takes the
23 tick 4 days of feeding, and 10 days of sitting before
24 the bacteria is eliminated in the tick.

25 It takes 2 to 3 days to transmit the disease

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1 to you. So the method of action that is publicized and
2 in the package insert by the own publication that it
3 references, doesn't work.

4 I am concerned, too, that there was blood
5 taken out of this trial and patented for personal profit,
6 and for other people that were not in the trial, and I
7 am concerned about our ability to get FOI information
8 from the FDA, which is heavily redacted.

9 However, I would like to say that Karen
10 Mittune -- and I don't know if she is here, or if I am
11 even saying her name right -- had an incredibly tough
12 job, and from the paper trail that we saw, every day was
13 busy trying to protect the public interest in this
14 material.

15 It was an extraordinary effort, and I am
16 telling you that I am glad that I am paying her salary
17 with my tax dollars, and I would gladly raise my tax
18 dollars if you guys would give her a raise and more power.

19 I am not done. One second.

20 CHAIRMAN DAUM: I think we all share that
21 view.

22 MS. FORSCHNER: In conclusion, I believe
23 that it is now time to recall the vaccine. If anyone
24 wanted a vaccine it would be me, and if anyone believes
25 that this vaccine, based on the science and not emotion,

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1 is not fit for consumption it would be any of us that
2 are in the community, the scientific community.

3 I believe that the FDA and the Vaccine
4 Advisory Committee should never ever let a pharmaceutical
5 get away with promising studies tomorrow, for an approval
6 today, and what I call the Whimpy effect, which if you
7 remember him from Popeye was constantly promising to pay
8 tomorrow for the hamburger today.

9 I would thank you for the time speaking today,
10 and I hope that you can take this under advisement as
11 a committee and as an FDA. Thank you.

12 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Ms. Vanderhoof-Forschner, we
13 thank you, and our third speaker --

14 MS. FISHER: Dr. Daum, I would like to make
15 just a comment. As a consumer representative, I really
16 feel like I need to make the comment if I could.

17 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Well, we have
18 representatives from all different factions, Ms. Fisher.
19 Why does that make you any different?

20 MS. FISHER: You allowed a comment on the
21 last statement.

22 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Please make your comment.

23 MS. FISHER: Thank you. As I said, as a
24 consumer representative, I think I do need to make a
25 comment. I know Karen Forschner, and the work that she

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1 has done for many years to promote the development of
2 a safe and effective Lyme disease vaccine that would
3 prevent other children from dying like her son did.

4 And I don't think that she would be coming
5 forward here today if she did not have good evidence about
6 the licensed Lyme vaccine and that it was hurting people.

7 Her assertion in this document, which I only
8 saw a couple of minutes ago, unfortunately, that there
9 was an application for a patent for Lyme disease vaccine
10 filed in March of 2000 that indicated that there is a
11 population of individuals who are genetically at risk
12 for developing autoimmune after vaccination is a very
13 serious assertion.

14 And if this was known nearly 2 years ago,
15 then the FDA and this Committee should have been given
16 the information so that at the very least there could
17 have been a labeling change made, because in the last
18 two years there have been many people who have gotten
19 the vaccine, and they could have been given the
20 information that they were genetically at risk for having
21 a reaction.

22 And I don't know at this point what procedure
23 is followed, but I think that the committee does need
24 to reconsider all of the information so that we can
25 potentially do something about it.

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1 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much, Ms.
2 Fisher. Our third and last to my knowledge speaker for
3 the open public hearing is Mr. Sheller, of the law firm
4 of Sheller, Ludwig & Badey, who has asked to speak to
5 the Committee also about Lyme disease vaccine, I believe,
6 for 5 minutes. Mr. Sheller, welcome.

7 MR. SHELLER: Yes, thank you. I might
8 mention that I am somewhat familiar with the other issues,
9 the gynecological issues, that you are talking about,
10 and I might suggest to the committee unrelated to my
11 comments on LYMERix, but related, that you should consider
12 calling for your own advice Dr. Charles Magnan, a
13 gynecological oncologist.

14 And my background is that my wife did the
15 original logo for the gynecological oncology surgery
16 group. And John Macuda. I think they have some opinions
17 on this, because we have talked about this, and I think
18 you need to start to look at bringing outside people in
19 and not just those that the FDA presents on their agenda.

20 I think you will get some really good
21 information from these people. Those are top surgeons
22 in gynecological oncology from Philadelphia. They have
23 an opinion on this, and would love to help you with it.

24 Let me get on with my comments. On January
25 31st of this year, I was privileged to have the opportunity

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1 to address this Committee to discuss the numerous serious
2 adverse reactions that have been experienced by
3 individuals vaccinated with SmithKline's (sic) vaccine,
4 LYMERix.

5 At the conclusion of that meeting, many of
6 you made serious significant and substantial
7 recommendations to the FDA to help better inform the
8 medical community and protect the general public from
9 the potential serious risks of this vaccine.

10 Now, 10 months later, the FDA has yet to
11 implement any of these recommendations, nor has the
12 manufacturer taken heed of the committee members'
13 admonitions regarding both the safety and efficacy of
14 LYMERix.

15 The circumstances surrounding FDA's approval
16 and continual endorsement of this vaccine are now becoming
17 disturbingly reminiscent of the case of Lotronex,
18 another GlaxoSmith (sic) product which was recounted in
19 a commentary in the May 19th, 2001 issue of the journal,
20 Lancet, entitled, "Lotronex and the FDA: A Fatal Erosion
21 of Integrity."

22 It was noted that in the case of Lotronex
23 that private communications appear to have subverted
24 official procedures, while suppressed scientific debate
25 has superseded a full and open review process.

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1 The FDA's and FlaxoSmithKline's failure to
2 act upon your recommendations is even more troubling given
3 the information that has come to light in the past 10
4 months, much of which was known at the time of your hearing
5 in January, and even at the time of the hearing in 1998,
6 and not brought to your attention.

7 Let me bring to your attention the fact that
8 there in the Journal of Rheumatology, in the November
9 2001 issue, a case report series by Dr. Carlos Rose, and
10 Paul Fawcett, and Kathleen Gibney, at the Alfred DuPont
11 Hospital for Children, confirming the adverse reactions
12 of arthritis caused by this vaccine.

13 You can read the article if you haven't read
14 it already. Dr. Fawcett and Dr. Rose offered to come
15 to this FDA meeting, and offered to come to the FDA and
16 talk to Dr. Mittune and to whoever they want, as did Dr.
17 Donald Marx, M.D., Ph.D., head of the Connaught Research
18 Study, as did Dr. Schell, and as did numerous other medical
19 professionals who know as much as anybody in the world
20 about this LYMERix vaccine.

21 The FDA refused to meet with them. I think
22 that is disgraceful. Now, I don't know what their reasons
23 are, but that has got to stop, and it is up to this
24 committee not to be manipulated into just accepting the
25 material which is put in front of their nose and having

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1 the people come before them that the FDA's representatives
2 has chosen to allow you to hear.

3 Now, let me take you back a step, and I am
4 skipping over the statement. You can read a lot of it.

5 Some of it comes from the New England Journal, and I
6 recommended that some of those people should have been
7 called in here.

8 And you ought to ask why Dr. Steere didn't
9 come in and tell you why he is not getting the vaccination
10 himself. Interesting, isn't it? He lives in Boston,
11 I think, and I think he visits Cape Code I would assume.

12 Now, let me take you back. The FDA has a
13 study of the risk of LYMERix, which continues to proceed
14 at a slower than a snail's pace, and although I was unable
15 to attend the American College of Rheumatology meeting
16 this month in San Francisco, I understand the presentation
17 of Dr. Platt's Phase IV cohort study of LYMERix continues
18 to suffer from low enrollment, well below the 25,000
19 vaccinee target established by the FDA, and shows no signs
20 of acceleration.

21 The FDA's own study of a small portion of
22 the vaccine adverse event reporting system reports,
23 initially discussed by Dr. Robert Ball of the FDA at the
24 January 31st meeting, continues to raise serious
25 questions.

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1 Initially the study only appears to be
2 looking at reports of arthritis and arthralgia, and not
3 the non-specific pain syndromes and developments of Lyme
4 disease-like symptoms, including neurological conditions
5 such as Bell's palsy, optic neuritis, and acute transverse
6 myelitis.

7 We have heard from numerous individuals who
8 experienced these symptoms shortly after vaccination with
9 LYMERix. In fact, you heard that a large group of them
10 come in here on January 31st, and I can tell you that
11 several of them have gotten worse and none have gotten
12 better.

13 However, this large population of adverse
14 reactions is apparently being ignored at this time. The
15 FDA has reportedly identified 415 VAERS reports which
16 are coded as arthralgia or possibly arthritis.

17 However, as of the Rheumatology convention
18 in mid-November of this year, they had only completed
19 the interviews of 49 of these people, and had complete
20 medical records only 31 of those 49.

21 Therefore, even the very limited study of
22 this small arthritis subgroup was proceeding very slowly.

23 However, despite these problems in the study design and
24 implementation by the FDA, it nevertheless identified
25 out of these 31 people on whom they have complete

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1 interviews and collected full medical records, 14 with
2 physician-diagnosed definite arthritis.

3 According to the FDA, 7 of those 14 cases
4 of physician diagnosed definite arthritis could not
5 plausibly be attributed to any other cause or concomitant
6 condition other than LYMERix. Nothing is in the label
7 about this.

8 Now, I can go on. There were other cases
9 they identified, and they were eliminated possibly
10 because they had some familiar history of the
11 immune-mediated disease or inflammatory arthritis.

12 These seven people also may very well
13 constitute cases of LYMERix induced arthritis, which
14 would bring the incidence rate of arthritis of 45.2
15 percent, 14 of 31 completed interviews with records; and
16 projected out to a total of 187 cases of LYMERex induced
17 arthritis for this small group of 415 reports.

18 That would present much higher numbers than
19 those which prompted Dr. Wayne Ray to make his comment
20 back in January of the unusually high number of adverse
21 reactions in VAERS reports that he found that is a red
22 flag, and I am quoting his words, "red flag."

23 When one considers the generally accepted
24 notion that as few as 10 percent of all adverse reactions
25 are ever reported, together with the fact that FDA has

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1 excluded from its study the Lyme disease like adverse
2 reactions which have actually been reported, and the fact
3 that many of the individuals who have reported adverse
4 reactions have never been contacted.

5 And I keep writing to the FDA on how come
6 you have not contacted most of my clients, like 95 percent
7 of them. It is clear that the results of this study will
8 grossly understate the actual occurrence of serious and
9 severe adverse reactions.

10 In fact, beyond the issue of arthritis and
11 Lyme-like symptoms, I am aware of several individuals
12 who have experienced crippling acute transverse myelitis,
13 ALS-like symptoms, and other de-myelinating syndromes
14 which were undoubtedly triggered by the immune response
15 to the OspA.

16 In light of the questionable and short-term
17 efficacy of the vaccine, according to the manufacturer's
18 own principal investigator, a vaccine which poses such
19 risks should not be on the market.

20 And to the extent that the FDA is taking the
21 position that individuals with a familial history of
22 immune-mediated disease or inflammatory arthritis, and
23 prior history of physician-diagnosed Lyme disease, cannot
24 have their post-LYMERix arthritic symptoms accurately
25 diagnosed, and at the very least LYMERex should be

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1 contraindicated for such people because of that.

2 The FDA's failure to bring the critical
3 information outlined in this submission to the attention
4 of the committee, and the substantial flaws in the FDA's
5 own study of VAERS reports, and the FDA's failure to insist
6 that GlaxoSmithKline comply with its Phase IV safety
7 surveillance obligation, or withdraw the LYMERix until
8 such compliance is achieved, raises the specter of the
9 subversion of official procedures and suppression of
10 scientific debate complained of in the Lancet this year
11 in May.

12 As is demonstrated in that article, the FDA
13 essentially sacrificed the credibility and integrity of
14 CDER to accommodate the wishes of GlaxoSmithKline for
15 Lontronex. I fear the same may be happening here, and
16 I would commend to you that there is a representative
17 of NCI here.

18 And I was heavily involved in this NCI report
19 that issued yesterday on smoking, and light, and low-tar
20 cigarettes. I was the guy who discovered the documents
21 that led to this report, and I can tell you that they
22 have a much more open process.

23 Much more open. They bring in people from
24 all over to get information. Judy Wokenfell from the
25 FDA, who is now retired, she was terrific. She didn't

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1 wait. She asked for anybody that had information to come
2 into the FDA and talk to them, and bring them the
3 documents, and bring them what they had to know, and that
4 was on February 3rd of 1999.

5 Don Shopplip, from NCI, what he did, he was
6 at those meetings, as was NCI and FDA people, and that
7 is what you should be doing as this committee. You need
8 to hear from the experts and others who have information,
9 and not just those who the FDA vaccine people want to
10 put in front of your nose. Thank you.

11 CHAIRMAN DAUM: Thank you very much, Mr.
12 Sheller, and in the spirit of fairness, we will offer
13 one comment if there needs to be one from a committee
14 member or sponsor. Okay. Thank you very much.

15 So I think in terms of addressing the FDA
16 questions that are the agenda of the meeting today, we
17 have made a lot of progress, and I think we are prepared
18 to explore tomorrow morning issues which we are uncertain
19 about, and then move on to hearing from each temporary
20 voting member and committee member about their views on
21 the two FDA questions.

22 We will also have an open session on the
23 laboratory of bacterial toxins here at FDA, and I have
24 arranged for that review and discussion to follow our
25 completion of discussion on the two questions related

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1 to HPV.

2 So I am hoping to start promptly at 8:30,
3 and that everybody will be bright-eyed and ready to go,
4 and thank you very much for you participation and comments
5 today.

6 (Whereupon, at 5:08 p.m., the Open Session
7 Meeting was concluded.)

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